

DIRECTIONS D3.3:

Report on DC Protection for Electrical Energy Hubs

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Executive Summary

Introduction

This report presents the methodology for protection system design for electrical energy hubs, developed in *Task 3.3 - Methodology for energy hub protection design and analysis* of DIRECTIONS Work Package 3. The proposed methodology builds on existing core research for HVDC protection system design, while addressing key challenges and benefits related to electrical energy hubs. The full methodology is structured as a phased design process, with each phase consisting of a dedicated method developed for the efficient design of key aspects of DC protection systems. This deliverable reports on the general structure of the methodology, which was derived based on a thorough literature review and categorization of existing methods. It then presents an example application of this design structure, using relatively straightforward methods within each design phase. Finally, innovative methods for conceptual and component-level protection system design are presented. These were developed, based on the insights of *Task 3.1* and *Task 3.2*, considering the specific challenges of electrical energy hubs, using the framework of the overall methodology. Therefore, the overall structure, methods, and examples presented in this deliverable together form a comprehensive method for protection system design in electrical energy hubs, as well as for future HVDC systems generally.

Key Contributions

Review of HVDC Protection System Design Methods and Requirements and Structure for Phased Co-Design Methodology

The structure of the full protection system design methodology is proposed based on a detailed review of existing methods. The literature is analyzed and distributed into three main design categories: *system-level conceptual design*, *component-level detailed design* and *system-level performance evaluation*. These categories form the basis for the design phases of the full methodology. For

each phase, the key design aspects, metrics, tools and interdependencies are analyzed. Therefore, the review provides a very clear overview of the requirements, purpose and role of the newly developed design methods

Illustration of Protection System Design Structure for Electrical Energy Hub Case Studies

The full protection system design methodology is illustrated for an electrical energy hub case study. Although this application of the methodology does not use the advanced design methods developed in this project, it serves as a valuable application of the theoretical findings from the literature. The phased design structure is illustrated, showing how the different aspects of the design can be separated while clearly indicating the dependencies and complementarity between them. The presented initial application of the methodology is used as key input for *Work Package 6* on the design of *DC Protection of the Belgian Energy Hub*, which combines the structure of the case study with the advanced design methods also proposed in this document.

Optimization Method for System-Level Conceptual Protection System Design in Electrical Energy Hubs

A mixed-integer linear optimization method is proposed as a novel tool for system-level conceptual protection system design. This method follows from the findings presented in *Deliverable 3.1* and builds on the current practice of using selected configurations of HVDC circuit breakers based on pre-defined protection strategies. In contrast to existing methods, the proposed optimization methods offers significantly more flexibility and allows the consideration of large numbers of relevant operating conditions. It is therefore expected to lead to more effective, optimal design outcomes.

The optimization problem is formulated to minimize the risk of high impact DC faults, represented by the temporary loss of power transfer between connected grids. The method is illustrated with a case study that shows how it allows the calculation of the optimal number of HVDC circuit breakers for a given electrical energy hub. Moreover, the results can be used to calculate the marginal benefit of each additional breaker relative to the fault impact risk. A sensitivity analysis performed using this optimization tool also provides additional key insights into the trade-offs between DC circuit breaker costs, DC grid failure rates, and fault impact risk in connected AC grids.

Hybrid Analytical-EMT Method for Efficient Component-Level Design of HVDC Protection Systems

Protection system design for multi-terminal HVDC grids is challenging due to the complexity of the system and the often conflicting design requirements. Effective specification of protection component parameters (e.g., DC circuit breakers and series DC inductors) during component-level design is crucial due to interdependencies among components, the need for detailed modeling, and the complex interactions between the protection system and converter control systems. Both analytical and simulation-based approaches have been proposed as solutions for component-level design. However, analytical methods may not accurately represent system behavior given that approximation is necessary, and simulation-based approaches often require extensive computational effort and time. Therefore, an efficient systematic component-level design method that combines both approaches is proposed. First, a fundamental analytical solution is derived to consider the protection system requirements. Then, a hybrid analytical-EMT methodology is proposed to accelerate convergence toward the required design parameters, after which detailed models are applied to ensure accuracy in design and validation. The approach is can be applied generally in electrical energy hubs, using the outcomes of the system-level conceptual design phase.

Chapter 1

Introduction and Motivation

As the importance of HVDC systems in the energy transition increases, these systems are becoming more interconnected and consequently more complex than typical point-to-point links. Future multiterminal HVDC grids and novel concepts such as electrical energy hubs are therefore expected to require complex design considerations for elements that have not been present in HVDC systems in the past, such as selective HVDC line protection systems.

These protection systems are required to prevent high impact outages when a DC fault occurs. They are significantly more expensive compared to AC protection. Therefore it is important to carefully consider their design to minimize costs while keeping the system secure. Therefore, this deliverable presents a methodology for protection system design for electrical energy hubs. This methodology is structured as a phased approach that allows maximum flexibility and efficiency in each part of the protection system design. The requirements for the different parts of the methodology have been derived through an analysis of existing methods, as discussed in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 presents an example application of the methodology framework to illustrate the phased design approach.

In each step of the phased design process, the relevant parts of the protection system design should be performed as efficiently as possible, while considering the key challenges specifically related to electrical energy hubs. Therefore, two innovative design methods that each represent one phase of the overall methodology have been developed and are presented in this report. Chapter 4 discusses a novel risk-based optimization method for HVDC circuit breaker topology optimization in electrical energy hubs. An efficient hybrid EMT-analytical method for component-level detailed design is proposed in Chapter 5. As discussed in these chapters, these methods both outperform similar existing methods that can be linked to their respective design phases, either in optimality of the design or in efficiency and cost of the design process. Consequently, they can be integrated into the framework presented in Chapters 2 and 3 to form a complete and effective protection

system design methodology for electrical energy hubs.

Figure 1.1 summarizes the content of this deliverable and positions the subsequent chapters with respect to the proposed protection system design methodology.

Figure 1.1: Overview of content in this deliverable and positioning of chapters in the protection design methodology structure

The content in this deliverable is based on the following papers:

- M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, "Review of (co-)design methods for HVDC protection systems," in: CIGRE NRCC Symposium 2025, Trondheim (NO), 2025. [1]
- M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, "Protection system design for an electrical energy hub case study," in: CIGRE Session 2026, Paris (FR), 2026. [2]
- M. Van Deyck, T. Van Acker, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, "Topology Optimization for DC Circuit Breaker Placement in HVDC Switching Stations," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2606.14286*, 2026. [3]
- A. Mohammadi, M. Van Deyck, G. Chaffey, D. Van Hertem, "Hybrid Analytical-EMT Method for HVDC Protection System Component-Level Design," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2605.11174*, 2026. [4]

Chapter 2

Review of (Co-)Design Methods for HVDC Protection Systems

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, “Review of (co-)design methods for HVDC protection systems,” in: CIGRE NRCC Symposium 2025, Trondheim (NO), 2025. [1]

2.1 Introduction

High voltage DC (HVDC) systems are becoming increasingly important in the energy transition, e.g. for offshore wind integration, grid reinforcement, or system interconnection [5]. These systems are becoming more complex than the typical point-to-point links that have been implemented in the past given that more multiterminal HVDC (MTDC) grids are now under development [6]. In contrast to previous HVDC systems, these MTDC grids are increasingly required to be expandable [7], multivendor, and interoperable [8]. To accommodate these requirements, new grid concepts such as electrical energy hubs (also sometimes called energy islands) [9] or HVDC switching stations [10] have been introduced. In these new kinds of systems, complex design considerations may be required for e.g. the protection system, more so than has been the case for point-to-point HVDC links in the past. The increased complexity of multiterminal grids compared to point-to-point links is illustrated in Figure 2.1 which illustrates example protection-related considerations for an example multiterminal HVDC grid.

The technology for HVDC protection, including HVDC circuit breakers (DCCB), has strongly evolved in recent decades and has gone from being one of the key obstacles to the implementation of MTDC grids [11] to being

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the increase in protection-related considerations for multiterminal HVDC grids

implemented in several grids in China [12–14]. Moreover, manufacturers are offering commercial HVDC circuit breakers [15, 16], while several HVDC switching stations that are likely to implement DCCBs are under development in Europe [17–19].

As the technology for HVDC protection has gradually developed and matured [20–22], fundamental insights into the key characteristics of faults [23, 24], requirements for converter stations [25], and fault-clearing strategies [26] have been developed. These insights have allowed the numerous relevant aspects for the design of HVDC protection systems to be considered in protection design studies and methodologies.

Since HVDC systems are becoming more complex, there is an increased need to consider typical HVDC protection aspects together with other system aspects, such as switching station topology or converter design, i.e. so-called co-design methods. Such co-design methods are expected to focus on the simultaneous design of several components or system-level aspects that exhibit a clear mutual influence. Consequently, this chapter aims to define the co-design requirements for future HVDC protection design methodologies by identifying the main inputs and outcomes of various studies in the literature and assessing the key interactions between parameters within each study, while also taking into account how these inputs and outputs are influenced by previous and subsequent stages in the design.

Though existing studies on protection system requirements often consider the impact of several system aspects, there is no structured co-design methodology that indicates which aspects are essential to consider together and how system developers should approach the design of complex MTDC systems. This chapter aims to offer the basis for such a structured co-design

methodology by presenting a review of existing HVDC protection (co-)design methods.

Several existing studies have provided a basis for co-design methods by evaluating the mutual influence of parameters in HVDC protection systems. An analysis of important HVDC protection aspects has been performed in [27], where the impact of different protection system parameters on the DC voltage and current transients is studied. Key interactions between converter properties and control modes and their effects on the DC fault-ride-through (FRT) behavior of converters have been studied in [28]. Additionally, an optimization method that allows the co-design of protection algorithms, DCCBs, reactors and surge arresters is presented in [29]. These examples of co-design methods and studies highlight the importance of considering several aspects together during HVDC grid design. However, these detailed studies still rely on decisions and assumptions about parts of the design that take place on a more conceptual level (e.g. the grid topology or protection configuration). Moreover, several system-level evaluation studies might be required to fully validate the design choices. Therefore, this chapter aims to further prepare the creation of a comprehensive and structured co-design methodology for HVDC systems by categorizing the required studies into three main design phases, which are further discussed in Section 2.2.

Sections 2.3-2.5 present a review of protection design methods from literature, related to each of the established design phases, for which the key considerations related to co-design are analyzed. Using these findings, Section 2.6 proposes a possible approach for the further development of future co-design methodologies for HVDC protection systems.

2.2 Classification of Protection Design Methods

Co-design requirements for HVDC protection systems can be identified within different parts of the overall design process. However, distinctions can also be made between different design phases that inherently follow a sequential structure. These design phases are expected to rely on inputs or assumptions from previous phases, while providing key inputs to subsequent parts of the design. Therefore, in this report, the design is split into three phases – system-level conceptual design, component-level detailed design, and system-level performance evaluation. A review of existing methods is presented with the goal of identifying requirements for co-design and establishing the key objectives of studies within each phase.

System-level conceptual design methods focus on the grid layout and configuration of the system. This includes the high-level grid topology, i.e. how many lines are placed in the grid and where they connect, the converter configuration, i.e. monopolar or bipolar and the grounding configuration,

and the substation topology, which also includes the placement and configuration of fault-clearing equipment such as DCCBs. These aspects are considered at this stage, since they determine the selectivity of the protection system, which follows from the possible pre-fault power flows and the design of DC-side protection zones [30, 31]. Such conceptual studies lead to a conceptual outline of the system that can be represented by a system-level diagram.

Component-level detailed design studies evaluate the requirements of specific components in the system and commonly require detailed electrical simulations or calculations. While component-level detailed design studies often investigate the mutual influence of the design of different components in the system, these studies also rely on previously determined conceptual grid designs and require assumptions on system-level aspects.

Protection systems are required to support and maintain the proper functioning of the rest of the system. Therefore, they are, in the final design stage, evaluated using system-level performance evaluation methods. Such methods focus on the fully designed protection system, with both the conceptual implementation and component ratings determined, and evaluate the performance using system-level KPIs that extend beyond the scope of initial conceptual studies.

Figure 2.2 summarizes the main aspects considered in each design phase. These aspects are expected to serve as inputs in subsequent design studies. Existing methods and co-design requirements within each design phase are evaluated based on literature in the following sections.

Figure 2.2: Examples of the main aspects considered in each design phase

2.3 System-Level Conceptual Design Methods

2.3.1 Design Aspects and Metrics in Conceptual Design Methods

The requirements for the design of HVDC protection systems are described in [32]. The main areas of design are identified as the technology for DC fault clearing, i.e. the implementation of DCCBs, fault blocking converters [33], or other principles such as preventive decoupling [34]; the protection strategy, relating to the selectivity of the fault clearing and the configuration of protection zones; and the type of protection algorithm for the detection and localization of faults. These identified design aspects relate to the conceptual implementation of the protection systems and take place at the system level. Consequently, system-level conceptual design studies can be defined as studies focusing on any of these aspects, as identified in [32], or considering additional system-level aspects such as the system reliability [35] or the busbar topology [36], which may also depend on market-related aspects and therefore require a co-design approach.

Key performance indicators for conceptual HVDC protection design studies have been established in the PROMOTioN project [37]. They are classified as indicators for *effectiveness*, *cost*, and *failure*. The effectiveness refers to the capability of the protection system to interrupt faults and limit the impact on connected systems. Performance metrics contributing to this are the transient energy imbalance in connected grids, the fault detection and interruption time, and the restoration times for active and reactive power transfer and the DC voltage. Cost KPIs commonly include the CAPEX for the protection system, which is expected to be dominated by the cost of DCCBs, but can also refer to operational costs related to losses, maintenance, or the cost of fault mitigation by e.g. reserve activation. Failure KPIs could be used to measure the reliability of the protection system and outline the protection sequence in case the primary protection fails to operate or clear the fault. The design aspects highlighted in [32] and the KPIs introduced in [37] are summarized in Figure 2.3. They are used as the basis for the analysis of other system-level conceptual design methods in the following subsection.

When using these KPIs to study the conceptual design aspects highlighted in [32], a wide range of additional factors may influence the outcomes of the design and must therefore be considered. These extra inputs may concern the faults for which protection systems are designed, i.e. which types of faults and fault locations are considered, as well as more external aspects such as optimal power flows, weather data, overall system layout and grid inertia in connected AC systems. The following review investigates how these different design aspects, KPIs and other dependencies are evaluated in existing system-level conceptual protection design methods and studies.

Figure 2.3: Overview of design aspects and KPIs for system-level conceptual design methods based on [32, 37]

2.3.2 Review of System-Level Conceptual Design Methods

Existing conceptual protection design methods consider different parts of the design requirements established in [32] with performance indicators that can be situated within the three main KPI categories from [37]. An example method for the assessment of conceptual protection designs is presented in [38], where an example HVDC grid is thoroughly evaluated using a conceptual analysis based on *protection matrices* that represent the response of each HVDC converter based on the fault separation concepts defined in [39], and time-domain electromagnetic transient (EMT) simulations. These EMT simulations, performed for different protection strategy implementations using various technologies for fault current interruption, allow a detailed evaluation of KPIs. However, such simulations pose a high computational load, thus limiting the number of possible implementations that can be considered. Moreover, the evaluated implementations must be selected based on expert choices and require many assumptions on the component-level. Therefore, though this method focuses on the evaluation of conceptual aspects of the protection system, there is in this case a co-design requirement with the component-level detailed design phase.

In [40], a more conceptual approach is taken to evaluate the AC grid impact, based on several *effectiveness* KPIs, caused by converter outages and cable faults under different protection strategies. The study presented in [41] adds to this analysis by evaluating the effectiveness of several protection strategies for different AC grid inertia and reserve capability conditions. A conceptual analysis of the transient energy imbalance based on the protection strategy and protection zone size is performed and mathematically formulated. Using a frequency response model to represent the AC grid impact and the effect of reserve availability, clear requirements for the HVDC protection system are set.

An optimization-based approach to conceptual HVDC protection design

is proposed in [42]. By integrating the investment cost for DCCBs and the cost for AC reserve activation as a representation of the fault impact into an objective function, this method aims to design an HVDC protection system such that the cost of maintaining AC grid stability is minimized. A frequency response model is required for the analysis and two selected protection strategies, with two possible active power restoration times for each, are considered.

The protection design method in [36] focuses on cost KPIs for the development of a modular protection design for offshore electrical energy hubs. The protection strategy is first chosen based on transient energy imbalance limits set by the AC system constraints. Subsequently, a specific implementation of the selected strategy is determined based on estimated CAPEX and OPEX costs for the protection components. The focus of this method is mainly on the selection of a busbar topology.

In [35], a fundamentally different approach is taken to the conceptual HVDC protection design. Different HVDC grid layouts are considered, and assumptions are made on the requirements for HVDC protection technology. For these predetermined grid and protection configurations the overall reliability, including the failure probability of the protection equipment itself, is evaluated. Moreover, the total expected electrical losses in the system, which are also influenced by the presence of additional protection components, are evaluated. The impact of contingencies is represented by the expected energy not served, which depends on the fault probabilities and repair times of the different elements in the system. Using these metrics, a sequential Monte Carlo technique is applied to find the grid layout and related protection concept that allows the maximum total power transfer. It should be noted that, although the scope of this design method extends beyond solely the HVDC protection system, key insights may be generated by this kind of study on the requirements for HVDC protection and the possibility to achieve a similar effectiveness of the overall HVDC grid with fewer requirements on the protection by carefully designing the overall HVDC grid layout.

2.3.3 Analysis of System-Level Conceptual Design Methods

The considered system-level conceptual design studies represent a selection of methods from literature that fulfill the identified requirements of the conceptual design phase. They are summarized in Table 2.1, which shows that all discussed methods focus in some way on the design of a protection strategy using metrics that fall within the effectiveness KPI as defined in [32]. However, in depth review of these sources and the variety of applied methods show that there is no definitive way to carry out this design phase. In fact, the considered studies often consider different aspects of the same design

criteria and to different levels of detail. Moreover, various additional inputs may need to be considered since they are shown to impact the results of conducted conceptual design studies. Therefore, it can be concluded that, although the requirements for system-level conceptual design studies are clearly established [32] and KPIs for these studies are available [37, 38], there remains a need for a flexible co-design method with limited requirements for additional assumptions which can be repeated for various additional input conditions. Consequently, such a method should be computationally inexpensive and give clear insights on conceptual protection requirements, where possible without depending on a large amount of data from external systems or the component-level.

Table 2.1: Characteristics of system-level conceptual design methods

Source	Design aspect	KPIs	Method	Additional analysis
[37, 38]	Protection strategy Technology	Effectiveness	Conceptual analysis EMT simulation	Detailed component-level sizing
[40]	Protection strategy	Effectiveness	Conceptual analysis	/
[41]	Protection strategy Technology	Effectiveness Cost	Conceptual analysis Analytical evaluation	AC grid inertia Reserves sizing
[42]	Protection strategy Technology	Effectiveness Cost	Optimization	AC grid inertia Reserves sizing
[36]	Protection strategy	Cost	Conceptual analysis	Busbar configuration
[35]	Protection strategy	Effectiveness Cost Failure	Stochastic analysis	Grid layout Converter config. Weather-dependent repair time

2.4 Component-Level Detailed Design Methods

The component-level detailed design of HVDC protection systems concerns the dimensioning of components in a predefined conceptual implementation. Design studies in this stage require thorough insight into the electrical phenomena that occur during critical moments in the protection sequence and consequently rely on EMT simulations or extensive analytical methods. Moreover, strong interactions exist between the detailed design of different components which means that most component-level detailed design methods inherently co-design methods to some degree.

Existing studies have already investigated which component-level aspects have the biggest impact on the performance of the HVDC protection design. In [27], a parameter sensitivity analysis using the Elementary Effects method is used to determine which out of eleven component-level parameters has the most significant influence on DC transients after faults.

Parameters such as DC surge arrester sizing, converter blocking delay and cable length are found to have a key impact on the transient voltages in

the DC grid. In addition to these, the arm inductance, pre-fault power flow, and AC grid short-circuit level play a large role in the magnitude of transient overcurrents. This type of sensitivity analysis is essential for determining the key influences in the component-level design of protection system components. However, the high computational load makes it intractable to always consider all possible parameter combinations. Furthermore, although [27] presents a thorough sensitivity analysis with many considered parameters and conducted EMT simulations, [28] shows that the converter control mode, which is often not considered in detail in typical protection design studies, also has a large impact on the FRT behavior of converters and the performance of the protection system. Consequently, while existing co-design methods and sensitivity studies provide key insights in interdependencies within the component-level detailed protection system design, it remains difficult to consider all relevant aspects in a single study. Moreover, the number of aspects that can be considered may be dependent on the method used for the design, e.g. analytical calculations, EMT simulation, optimization, etc. Therefore, this section aims to contribute to existing knowledge on co-design requirements for component-level studies, not by performing in-depth technical evaluations, but through a meta-analysis of the literature, analyzing which aspects are most often considered together.

2.4.1 Review of Component-Level Detailed Design Methods

As previously discussed, [27] presents a sensitivity analysis of various protection system parameters using the elementary effects method. The considered parameters are categorized as control system, substation equipment, grid characteristics and fault topology parameters. Eleven parameters are considered, in addition to the transient fault current. All considered aspects are listed in detail in Table 2.2. It should be noted that, although some degree of converter controls is considered in [27], they are evaluated in significantly more detail through specially developed analytical models in [28]. This study evaluates the interactions between converter control modes and other converter properties, such as the overcurrent capability and the rating of internal components, and grid-related aspects such as the AC grid short circuit power and the number of adjacent lines.

In [29], an optimization method based on genetic optimization and embedded EMT simulations is developed specifically for the co-design of the threshold settings and margins of protection algorithms, the size of line inductors, and the surge arrester rating. Within this optimization formulation, several additional design constraints on the DCCB current, speed, and converter FRT are formulated.

Another clear example of a component-level detailed design study presents

a *systematic approach to HVDC breaker sizing* [43]. An analytical method that allows the calculation of fault currents in the frequency domain is applied to design the operating time, current rating, and energy absorption capability of DCCBs. These values are decided depending on the fault current limiting (FCL) inductor value and the converter FRT capabilities. Moreover, the effect of adding additional adjacent lines is investigated.

Similarly, [44] investigates the trade-off between DCCB current rating, breaker speed and FCL inductance by proposing a *reactor sizing criterion* that allows the continuous operation of converters, i.e. with no submodule blocking. A simplified converter model is used to derive an analytical expression of the maximum fault current and required inductance in the system. The breaker currents are calculated, simulated and tested experimentally in detail. However, all other parameters are kept constant, minimizing the co-design aspect of this study.

Another method that relies on the analytical calculation of fault currents – and can consequently be used to dimension DCCBs – is presented in [45]. Traveling wave theory is used to analytically describe the voltages and currents after a DC fault, focusing on the fault current contribution of capacitive components in the networks, which has been identified as the dominant contribution during the first milliseconds of the transient [23]. This method focuses on two-level converters and is therefore not directly applicable to modular multi-level converter-based systems. Nevertheless, by characterizing fault currents with analytical formulations, key dependencies on other system aspects, e.g. line length, fault resistance, or FCL inductance, immediately become clear in the formulations. However, this method is also limited by the applicability of the simplified grid models that can be characterized by analytical expressions. This makes it difficult to incorporate other co-design aspects that require more in-depth models, such as the contribution of converters to the fault current.

An EMT simulation-based sensitivity analysis of the influence of several parameters on the cable surge arrester requirements, i.e. energy dissipation rating and voltage, is presented in [46]. In [47], a conceptual and analytical evaluation of the key factors influencing DCCB design is presented. The energy dissipation requirement in DCCBs is highlighted as a key aspect that can have a large impact on the protection design and might even determine the feasibility of the HVDC protection system as a whole. Parameters such as FCL inductance, converter arm inductance, and AC short-circuit level (SCL) are addressed as key parameters for allowing the effective operation of DCCBs and preventing converter blocking, but the need for thorough co-design with the energy dissipation requirements and the robustness to AC-side faults is emphasized.

2.4.2 Analysis of Design Aspects

Table 2.2 presents a detailed overview of all studied design parameters that are considered in the listed component-level studies. The parameters are categorized here as relating to the converters, DCCBs, algorithms, DC grid, AC grid, and fault characteristics. The most considered design aspects are the DCCB current and FCL inductor, two parameters that have a clear influence on each other. It should be noted, however, that although the fault current through DCCBs is a key parameter in the protection design, the (maximum) DCCB rating is often not free for design by system developers since this is expected to be defined by manufacturers. Instead, most studies focus on sizing FCL inductors to keep the fault current within the interruption capability of the DCCB, or to adhere to the converter FRT requirement or minimum blocking time.

In studies that explicitly focus on the DCCB design [29, 43, 47], the DCCB speed and energy dissipation capabilities are key parameters. It is clear from these studies that the breaker design is also dependent on the FRT behavior of the converters, which is often characterized as the requirement to remain unblocked, or as a minimum time before submodule blocking occurs. Similarly to the conceptual design methods, there is a relative under representation of protection co-design methods that incorporate the algorithm design. Therefore, although DC fault detection and localization is an active field of study [48], within the literature it is not considered a critical part of the co-design studies which focus on the component-level DC protection system design. Likewise, converter control aspects other than the FRT are not usually considered. However, it is made clear in [27, 28] that the control system does influence the fault phenomena, while it is also indicated in [23, 35] that these effects can be neglected in the initial period of the fault transient. Consequently, future co-design methods need to carefully consider and establish the degree to which converters should be represented.

As could be expected, studies that focus specifically on evaluating interactions between different protection design parameters consider the widest variety of aspects [27, 28, 46]. Following those, [29] and [47] consider up to eight different variable parameters in the design of the protection system. A clear outlier is [44], which relies on assumptions for many of these parameters and simply compares the DCCB current and FCL inductance. As the number of considered parameters is reasonably similar for most of the considered studies, there is no single clear method, e.g. simulation, analytical analysis, optimisation, that proves the most suitable for co-design studies based on the performed analysis.

Table 2.2: Characteristics of component-level detailed design methods

Source		[27]	[28]	[29]	[43]	[44]	[45]	[46]	[47]	Occ.
Converter	Rating		x							1
	Control	x	x							2
	Overload capacity		x							1
	FRT		x	x	x				x	4
	Blocking time	x	x		x			x		4
	Arm reactor	x	x					x	x	4
DCCB	Current rating	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	7
	Speed			x	x				x	3
	Energy dissipation			x	x				x	3
Algorithm	Threshold			x						1
	Margin			x						1
DC grid	Line length	x					x	x		3
	Nb. Lines				x		x			2
	Line inductor (FCL)		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	7
	Line type							x	x	2
	DC capacitance						x			1
	Surge arrester	x						x		2
	Pre-fault power flow	x						x		2
AC grid	SCL	x	x				x	x	x	5
	Transformer reactance	x	x					x		3
Fault	Type	x								1
	Location	x	x	x						3
	Time	x	x							2
	Resistance						x			1
Total		12	12	8	7	2	7	9	8	

2.5 System-Level Performance Evaluation

2.5.1 The Aim of System-Level Performance Evaluation

System-level performance evaluation methods examine the performance of HVDC protection systems, assessing whether these systems operate as expected, and whether the design choices made in previous phases satisfy various system-level functional requirements for the HVDC and AC grids. The performance of HVDC protection systems can be validated in several ways. This section identifies three main types of evaluation methods that consider i) the operation of the protection system itself, ii) the HVDC grid impact, and iii) the AC grid impact. Figure 2.4 shows several examples of aspects that could be considered or validated in each of these categories.

2.5.2 Review of System-Level Performance Evaluation Methods

HVDC protection systems that have undergone both the system-level conceptual design, and the component-level detailed design must be thoroughly

Figure 2.4: Identified types of performance evaluation studies and example parameters to be validated

evaluated before they can be implemented. To this end, guidelines for HVDC protection test procedures are proposed in [49]. It is established that protection systems should be validated based on general functional requirements for protection systems which include sensitivity, selectivity, speed, reliability, seamlessness and robustness. The performance evaluation is carried out by applying several critical fault scenarios and pre-fault operational scenarios. As these general functional requirements show, the accurate detection and localizing of faults is essential to HVDC protection systems. Therefore, a methodology specifically for the validation of selective protection algorithms is proposed in [50]. In [51], an extensive performance evaluation method that relies on 31 total performance indicators is introduced. These indicators are categorized under reliability, fault monitoring, operational maintenance, control efficiency and system redundancy and are used to quantify the operational status of HVDC protection systems.

Although the focus of this report is on the development of protection systems rather than the development and testing of equipment, component-level evaluations are still essential to validating the operation of HVDC protection systems. As components such as DCCBs have matured throughout the past years, test requirements [52], test circuits [53], and test procedures [54] have been developed, aiming to ensure the proper functioning of this technology in future protection systems.

Besides the functioning of the protection system itself, it is also necessary to evaluate the impact on the HVDC grid stability and the connected AC grids. If continuous operation of the HVDC grid during and after the protection system operation is desired, converters must be able to maintain the required FRT behavior. Though FRT requirements play a key role in component-level studies, additional assessment of the FRT behavior may be required in the performance evaluation stage. Through the development of detailed FRT profiles and HVDC grid codes [55], clear requirements can be established for the DC voltage at converter terminals during and after DC faults. These can then be evaluated for critical scenarios. Additionally, in [56], a method for grid-level protection coordination is proposed, establishing different FRT requirements specifically for each converter in the considered HVDC grid. Thus, the DC FRT requirements are adapted to the considered HVDC grid,

and the protection system can be validated for these requirements.

Besides ensuring the expected behavior during the fault clearing sequence, protection systems must also allow effective post-fault recovery of the HVDC grid. In [57], a method for assessing DC voltage oscillations in the post-fault recovery period is presented. Evaluating such possible instabilities, which may not be expected or considered in earlier design phases, is essential for the development of protection systems.

Finally, dedicated performance evaluation studies that validate the AC grid stability are required in the system-level performance evaluation stage. As indicated in Section 2.3, the AC-side impact of DC faults is a key design metric in the conceptual design of protection systems. However, following the system-level and component-level design stages, evaluation studies on these impacts are required. These evaluation studies can rely on the detailed component parameters and system-level configurations set in previous design phases and can therefore perform a more detailed evaluation of performance metrics also used in other design phases. In [58], a method for the evaluation of AC grid stability, based on KPIs from [37, 38] is proposed. Additionally, [59] presents a method to evaluate the transient stability after DC faults and highlights that this metric is a key concern for *embedded* HVDC systems that connect to the same synchronous AC grid in several locations.

2.5.3 Discussion

System-level performance evaluation studies include a wide range of studies that evaluate various parts HVDC protection system and connected DC and AC grids. The conducted review shows that evaluation methods may consider a broad range of performance indicators not considered in the initial design phases, as well as previously used design parameters which are evaluated for additional scenarios or in more detail. Given the need to evaluate aspects related to the protection system, the overall HVDC grid, and the AC grid in a high number of scenarios, and to a sufficient level of detail, the selection of representative models and relevant scenarios is expected as a key part of performance evaluation studies.

Consequently, based on the performed analysis of key parameters for performance evaluation studies in this chapter, future studies can further develop efficient methods for identifying relevant models and scenarios for each metric in the system-level performance evaluation stage.

2.6 Towards a Co-Design Methodology

This report categorizes the design process for HVDC protection systems into three separate phases. These phases are defined based on clear differences

in the scope and objectives of studies in each phase. Moreover, there is a clear link between these phases as outcomes of one phase serve as inputs for subsequent studies. This input/output structure highlights the influence and dependence of design aspects on previous and subsequent design phases, which provides opportunities for iterative co-design. However, within the defined categories of HVDC protection design studies – system-level conceptual design, component-level detailed design, and system-level performance evaluation – there remains a need for a structured methodology that sets clear objectives for design studies and emphasizes the requirements for co-design of various considered design aspects. Through a review of example studies related to each design phase, an analysis of these objectives and co-design requirements has been performed.

In **system-level conceptual design** studies, there is a clear focus on the selectivity of the DC protection system and the configuration of protection zones. These are, in many cases, determined by the selection of a protection strategy, which determines the number and location of DCCBs in the system. The cost of these DCCBs is one of the main factors to consider for this decision and should be weighed against the *effectiveness* of the protection system. This effectiveness metric is commonly equated with how well the DC protection system mitigates the impact of faults in connected AC power systems. Many methods are available to quantify this impact, ranging from the calculation of the maximum transient energy imbalance to the representation of the AC grid response through dynamic models, EMT simulations, or economic cost functions that represent reserve activation and load shedding.

Though the choice of a protection strategy based on the protection system effectiveness and cost is a key element in the system-level conceptual design phase, there are several other aspects that can also be considered at this stage and may influence this choice. Considering more detailed aspects such as losses, reliability, and back-up protection may affect the protection strategy choice in the design. Moreover, high-level considerations on the system topology can also impact the protection requirements and should be considered. Consequently, conceptual protection design methods must be flexible and adaptable to many different inputs. This means that these studies should be computationally inexpensive and therefore not rely on detailed design aspects more than necessary. The need for a flexible methodology for conceptual protection design may require future studies to move away from expert-based concepts such as protection strategies towards open methods that determine the selectivity of the HVDC protection system as required based on the considered inputs.

Component-level detailed design studies focus on the electrical phenomena that are relevant to the proper functioning of components in the HVDC grid during the operation of the protection system. Due to the clear influence

of different components on these electrical phenomena, component-level studies inherently focus on the co-design of different design aspects and must consider many relevant scenarios. The most commonly considered aspects for the component-level design of HVDC protection systems are the line inductance for fault current limiting, and the fault current that must be interrupted by DCCBs. However, parameters relating to converters are also found to play a key role in the detailed design of these components in the protection system. Some studies evaluate the component-level influence of HVDC system-level aspects such as the number of lines, line length and the line types. Though it is important to be aware of the influence of these system-level aspects, it is expected that they would be determined as inputs in the system-level phase before the component-level design in a full protection design methodology. Additionally, some components that influence the protection system would be designed primarily to serve other aspects of the system and therefore function mainly as inputs in the detailed protection system design. Lastly, the influence of the considered scenarios on the detailed component-level design is highlighted in several studies by varying several fault parameters and pre-fault power flow conditions. Therefore, the parameters considered in Table 2.2, and other possible parameters for this design phase, can be divided into four groups when developing a co-design methodology for component-level detailed design studies, as shown in Figure 2.5. Design parameters can be taken either as inputs from the system-level design or set by other grid requirements, as part of the considered operational scenario, or as a component-level co-design parameter. The proposed structure of the listed parameters in these categories serves as an example in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Example structure of parameters and inputs for component-level studies

Based on this example structure, future co-design methodologies component-level detailed design may consist of three steps: i) defining the inputs from the system-level and other component-level requirements, ii) selecting critical scenarios, and iii) performing the co-design of relevant parameters through detailed simulations or analytical methods. In this context, future studies are required to determine how these steps are best to be conducted to come to an effective methodology for the component-level detailed design of HVDC protection systems.

Finally, **system-level performance evaluation** studies take a broader system-level perspective to validate the design choices made in the development of the HVDC protection system. These studies present the opportunity to investigate any interactions and dependencies that were neglected or simplified in the conceptual and component-level stages of the design. Similarly to the component-level studies, it is essential in this stage to establish which parameters require evaluation and which serve as (additional) inputs, and to establish the critical scenarios for which to perform this evaluation.

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter evaluates the need for co-design methods for future HVDC grid protection systems. Three main design phases are established in the development of a DC protection system design. By conducting a literature review of existing methods and studies, the main requirements and further challenges have been established for each design phase. These findings are used to present a basic structure for a complete co-design methodology that can be generally applied for the design of future systems. It has been found that such a methodology should be structured to have a clear distinction between the parameters considered in different phases of the design, which function as inputs for later studies. Based on this analysis, future studies working towards this methodology may improve the design of HVDC protection systems and expediate the development of complex, multiterminal HVDC grids.

Chapter 3

Protection System Design for an Electrical Energy Hub Case Study

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, “Protection system design for an electrical energy hub case study,” in: CIGRE Session 2026, Paris (FR), 2026. [2]

3.1 Introduction

High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) grids fulfill key functions for the integration of renewable energy sources into electrical systems. Their ability to efficiently transmit high amounts of electrical power over long distances is crucial for the connection of remote (offshore) renewable energy sources, on-shore grid reinforcement and the interconnection of different (asynchronous) market zones [6]. HVDC systems have, in the past, mainly consisted of point-to-point connections. However, future HVDC grids are increasingly expected to be multiterminal, allowing increased efficiency, robustness, and operational flexibility [11]. Rather than the top-down implementation of a European HVDC supergrid, the development of multiterminal HVDC grids is expected to occur in a phased approach [6], with existing point-to-point links being extended with additional terminals [60], or multiple point-to-point links being connected in a central DC switching station (DCSS) [18]. Additionally, plans for expandable, offshore electrical energy hubs (sometimes termed ‘energy islands’) have been proposed in recent years [61]. These offshore hubs facilitate the aggregation and integration of renewable energy sources through HVDC links and may serve as central connection points for future meshed HVDC grids.

The development of DCSS as an element of multiterminal HVDC grids leads to some important challenges compared to typical AC substations. The increased physical dimensions and costs of DC protection systems lead to a different balance of investment cost and system security. Consequently, the primary protection system implementation must be more thoroughly considered in the design, in contrast to AC grid protection which is largely standardized [62]. Previous research on existing methods for primary HVDC protection system design has shown that there is a wide range of design aspects to consider, for which various metrics can be used [1, 63]. Three main design phases were identified to classify existing methods and to serve as an outline for a full methodology for (co-)designing these different aspects.

First, system-level conceptual design methods determine the selectivity of HVDC protection systems, often expressed in terms of a protection strategy. These design methods generally consider the effectiveness of protection systems based on their ability to limit the impact of DC faults on the non-faulted part of the grid. This is typically weighed against the protection system cost, which depends on the technology used for fault clearing [1]. Secondly, component-level detailed design methods consider the electrical transients caused by DC faults for the optimal sizing of protection system components. These studies, which commonly take place in an electromagnetic-transient (EMT) simulation environment, depend on many parameters that influence the fault clearing process. Therefore, it is crucial to identify which parameters are of main interest in the design, which ones are set by other system requirements, and which inputs serve to define critical scenarios for the design studies.

Finally, system-level performance evaluation studies validate both the conceptual and detailed design decisions, using a framework that extends beyond the scope of the earlier design stages. The evaluation typically includes the operation of the protection system and its impact on the overall HVDC and AC grids [1].

This chapter presents a methodology and case study for protection system design in HVDC grids that contain a centralized DCSS with connections to several AC grids. The proposed methodology follows a three-phased structure described above, as first introduced in [1]. Dedicated methods for system-level conceptual design and component level detailed design are explained in Sections 3.2 and 3.3 respectively. In Section 3.4, the framework for the system-level performance evaluation is explained. Section 3.5 presents a case study in which these methods are applied.

3.2 System-Level Conceptual Design of HVDC Protection Systems

Interrupting and clearing faults is challenging in HVDC grids due to the lack of natural zero-crossings in the fault currents. For this reason, faults in existing point-to-point systems are cleared on the AC side using AC switchgear. On the DC side, the system discharges into the fault and the DC voltage is lost. This process can similarly be applied in multiterminal grids. Faults are interrupted at converter terminals, and the DC grid is de-energized. Subsequently, the faulted element can be cleared by disconnecter switches at (near) zero current. The DC voltage can then be restored and power transfer can resume through the non-faulted elements.

Such a *non-selective* (NS) protection system limits the permanent loss of power transfer caused by DC faults but leads to the temporary loss of the entire HVDC grid. In large multiterminal systems, this may be unacceptable, as it could cause a high loss of infeed (LoI) into the connected AC grids. Alternative approaches that offer selective fault interruption are possible using HVDC circuit breakers (DCCBs). These can, despite the lack of natural zero-crossings, forcibly interrupt fault currents and isolate the faulted element from the grid. This allows the non-faulted components to remain in continuous operation, leading to lower temporary LoI and lower AC grid impacts [26]. DCCBs are, however, significantly more expensive than their AC counterparts, which is why different strategies for selective DC protection have been proposed. *Fully selective* (FS) protection systems guarantee the continuous operation of all non-faulted grid elements. *Partially selective* (PS) protection systems use DCCBs to separate certain *protection zones* within the DC grid, allowing only the faulted protection zone to be de-energized [26]. Figure 4.1 illustrates an example HVDC protection sequence for each protection strategy. Note that, although the illustrative durations of each part of the protection sequence are shown as identical for the three protection strategies in this figure, the moments of interruption, isolation and restoration would, in reality, differ between these strategies. The figure shows that DC protection strategy primarily impacts the temporary LoI ($\Delta P_{transient}$), which occurs only for the duration of the protection sequence [40].

The maximum temporary LoI in AC grids is limited by the frequency containment reserves. Therefore, HVDC protection systems must be designed to limit fault impacts, while considering the trade-off with the (protection) system costs. In the context of a centralized DCSS, however, simply selecting a strategy for selectivity, as is commonly done in existing conceptual protection design methods [43, 44, 64, 65], does not guarantee a cost-effective design. The design flexibility of a substation with several connections of cables and converters allows different levels of selectivity to be achieved in many ways,

Figure 3.1: Example of HVDC protection sequence for different protection strategies

based on the configuration of DCCBs. Therefore, for the system-level conceptual design of DCSS, a method that goes beyond the selection of a pre-defined protection strategy is used in this chapter. DCCB configurations are *short-listed* using a conceptual algorithm that considers the trade-offs between the number of DCCBs (i.e. investment cost) and fault impacts on connected AC grids [64].

3.2.1 DCCB Configuration Shortlisting for HVDC Switching Stations

The shortlisting method used for conceptual design in this chapter was first introduced in [64]. This method relies on a simplified, graph-based representation of the grid to determine the selectivity requirements of the protection system in the DCSS. This grid representation, illustrated in Figure 3.2, allows the creation and evaluation of large numbers of configurations by varying the connection points of cables and converters within the DCSS. The design of the configuration of DCCBs and DC busbars within the DCSS, is automated to ensure all connecting components are optimally distributed into different protection zones.

With this simplified representation of the grid, the selectivity of the protection system can be automatically evaluated by determining the protection zones, which can be found as the collection of nodes bordered by fault-blocking edges (i.e. breakers), marked in light blue in the example configuration shown in Figure 3.3.

With this method, every possible DCCB configuration in a DCSS can be evaluated by calculating the temporary LoI when any one protection zone is lost. To evaluate this, the available power transfer capacity between external grid nodes is calculated for any DC fault, which causes the removal of the faulted protection zone, and compared to the pre-fault configuration.

Figure 3.2: Graph-based representation of an example HVDC grid with a central DC switching station [64]

Figure 3.3: Protection zones in example DCCB configuration based on fault-blocking edges [64]

The evaluation of DCCB configurations must be conducted for several pre-fault power flow scenarios. Moreover, besides the maximum total temporary LoI, other metrics can be considered. These include the fault-probability-weighted average impact and the average fault impact in case of DCCB failure. The full shortlisting method is structured as a filtering process in which power flow scenarios and fault-impact metrics are sequentially evaluated. Starting with every possible DCCB configuration for a given HVDC grid layout, possible designs are filtered for each power flow (PF) and impact metric, resulting in a shortlist of conceptual protection system designs that effectively limit fault impacts in all relevant conditions. This process is illustrated in Figure 3.4. Figure 3.4a outlines possible steps in the shortlisting process, while Figure 3.4b shows how this filtering gradually leads to a small number of

Figure 3.4: Illustration of filtering steps in the protection configuration shortlisting process [64]

applicable *lowest-impact configurations* for each considered DCCB count.

3.3 Component-Level Detailed Design of HVDC Protection Systems

The system-level conceptual design assumes that faults can always be cleared by fault-blocking equipment and that healthy (non-faulted) protection zones remain in continuous operation. Component-level detailed design must ensure the implementation meets this expected behavior by considering the electrical transients in the fault clearing process and specifying the requirements and ratings of components in the protection system.

3.3.1 Reactor Sizing for HVDC Switching Stations

Based on the review of component-level methods and the analysis of key design parameters performed in [1], five main co-design aspects are considered for the case study in this chapter: the DCCB current interruption capability ($I_{DCCB,max}$), the DCCB operating speed (t_{DCCB}), the overcurrent capability of converters (K), the line inductance at cable terminations and converter terminals, and the fault-current limiting inductance placed in series with the DCCB. Of these design parameters, only the inductance values are considered fully flexible. DCCB and converter parameters are selected as constraints, given the limited available industrial solutions for these tech-

nologies. This means that the component-level protection system design in this chapter aims to size the DC grid reactors such that the protection system, using a given DCCB technology and converter overcurrent limit, operates as expected. Based on assumptions about today's industrial systems, this chapter applies example requirements for the expected operation of the protection system [44], which can be summarized as:

1. DCCBs must be able to interrupt faults in neighboring protection zones
2. Converters in non-faulted protection zones must be able to remain in continuous operation (without submodule blocking) during the fault¹.

Both requirements are mainly relevant in the initial period after the fault, when cables and converters discharge and high fault currents arise (i.e. in the period between fault inception and interruption as shown in Figure 4.1). This discharge stage ends when the fault is interrupted, either by DCCBs or at the converter terminals. Therefore, the requirements imply that, in the period between fault inception (t_{Fault}), detection, and interruption (t_{DCCB}), (1) the current through DCCBs must remain below its maximum current interruption capability, and (2) the arm current in converters in non-faulted protection zones must remain below the overcurrent limit.

Given these requirements, reactors in the DC grid can be designed to ensure that fault currents are sufficiently limited for all critical fault scenarios. Moreover, since primarily the initial period of capacitive discharge is important for this study, simplified converter models can be used [43, 65]. However, as converter arm currents are not represented in these simplified models, a DC overcurrent limit at the converter terminals can be used instead [28, 43]. This current limit, typically formulated as Eq. (3.1), approximates the current at the DC terminal of converters when the maximum arm current is reached internally. Here, \hat{i}_{arm} represents the peak nominal arm current and K the overcurrent rating. Additionally, \hat{i}_{AC} represents the maximum AC-side contribution to the arm current during the fault. Depending on the converter control strategy, the maximum AC current may be set by the upper-level controls, e.g. for AC voltage support during faults [66]. For the case studies in this chapter, the value of \hat{i}_{AC} is estimated at 120% of the peak rated AC current. However, detailed analysis of the converter control system and fault response is required to fully validate the approximation in Eq. (3.1) for application in a real system.

$$I_{conv,DC,max} = 3 \cdot \left(K \cdot \hat{i}_{arm} - \frac{\hat{i}_{AC}}{2} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

¹While this requirement for converter fault-ride-through is considered relevant for this case study, other options such as allowing temporary blocking at all converters or no converter blocking at all could also be considered.

Using this representation of the converter overcurrent limit, the key protection system constraints used in the component-level detailed design can be formulated as:

$$I_{conv,DC,i}(t) \leq I_{conv,DC,max} \quad \forall \text{ converters } i \notin \text{Faulted zone}, t \in t_{Fault} : t_{DCCB} \quad (3.2)$$

$$|I_{DCCB,j}(t)| \leq I_{DCCB,max} \quad \forall \text{ DCCB } j, t \in t_{Fault} : t_{DCCB} \quad (3.3)$$

3.3.2 Selection of Critical Scenarios for DC Reactor Sizing

This section presents the application of an example component-level method to the case study considered in this chapter. Since the analysis in this chapter serves primarily to demonstrate the phased protection system design structure introduced in Chapter 2, a more simplified method is used, compared to the detailed one introduced in Chapter 5. Moreover, the critical fault scenarios are, in this chapter, only evaluated for one possible grid configuration, in which all converters are connected to the DC grid. Besides establishing the design parameters and constraints, the critical (pre-)fault scenarios for the component-level design must be determined. The scenario selection depends, in part, on the scope of the protection system itself, i.e. the (types of) faults the protection system is designed to clear. Similarly to [67], it is assumed that the protection system focuses only on pole-to-ground cable faults. Scenarios that include pole-to-pole cable faults are not studied, as these are typically considered as *exceptional contingencies* [67]. The representation of the AC-current contribution in Eq. (3.1) assumes maximum reactive power flow in converters to ensure a conservative design. Finally, only permanent, zero-impedance faults are considered, since these are expected to represent the worst-case conditions. Using these assumptions, critical scenarios for the study in this chapter can be defined based on the *fault location* and *pre-fault power flow*.

3.3.2.1 Critical Fault Location

The fault location determines which grid element is faulted, as well as the location of the fault along this element, i.e. the *fault distance* (F_x). The critical fault distance along each element can be defined as the fault location along a cable for which the magnitude of the fault currents through DCCBs and non-blocking converters are the highest.

At the location of a fault, a sudden drop of the DC voltage drop occurs. This creates a traveling wave that can be represented as a step signal with magnitude $-V_0$ (with V_0 the pre-fault voltage at the fault location). As this voltage wave propagates through the cable, the magnitude of the signal is attenuated exponentially. The reflection of the negative voltage wave may

increase the voltage drop experienced at the cable terminal for more remote faults compared to faults at the cable terminal [67]. After this initial reflection, the voltage at the terminal of the faulted cable (V_t) is given by:

$$V_t = V_{t,0} - V_0 \cdot e^{-\alpha \cdot F_x} \cdot (1 + \Gamma_t) \quad (3.4)$$

In this equation, α is the attenuation constant and Γ_t the reflection coefficient at the cable terminal. When the reflected voltage wave reaches the fault location, which in case of a zero-resistance fault has a reflection coefficient of -1, it is reflected back to the cable terminal, now as a positive voltage step. Consequently, the fault distance determines not only the attenuation of the voltage drop, but also the time between reflections. These principles can be used to determine which faults lead to maximum fault currents in DCCBs and converters. This analysis must be done on a case-by-case basis, since the configuration of the DCCBs, converters and cables impacts the traveling wave behavior, in order to draw a clear conclusion on whether multiple faults along lines must be considered for a specific case.

3.3.2.2 Critical Pre-Fault Power Flow

Many pre-fault power flow conditions can occur in a large DCSS. These must be considered in the design as they determine the initial conditions of currents in critical components. When designing the protection system such that the constraints formulated in Eq. (3.2) and (3.3) are met, pre-fault power flows that lead to maximum initial currents in the critical components should consequently be used.

3.3.3 Simulation-Based Reactor Sizing Based on Analytical Estimation

As inductance values are variable in the component-level design, the computational load of EMT simulations can be lowered by making initial estimations based on expected fault currents. Since reactor currents (I_L) can be generally expressed as in Eq. (3.5) (with ΔV_L the voltage across the reactor), the minimum inductance value can be estimated using Eq. (3.6) for reactors in series with elements with a maximum current limit [19].

$$I_L(t) = \frac{1}{L} \int_{t_{Fault}}^{t_{DCCB}} \Delta V_L(t) dt + I_L(t_{Fault}) \quad (3.5)$$

$$L \geq \frac{\Delta V_L}{I_{max} - I_L(t_{Fault})} \cdot \Delta t \quad (3.6)$$

Though ΔV_L can be estimated using the traveling wave-based principles expressed in Eq. (3.4), it is not possible, using these simplified analytical

methods, to fully determine the voltage at every point in the DC grid. Therefore, the estimation of minimum inductance values using Eq. (3.6) serves mainly as a starting point for the design in simulation. While this method is effective for relatively small case studies as considered in this chapter, it is expected that more complex component-level methods are required for the detailed design of larger HVDC grids in the future.

3.4 HVDC Protection System Design Validation

The system-level and component-level design methods both use simplified models in select critical scenarios. A full performance evaluation method should provide a detailed validation of the protection system operation, the DC grid impact, and the AC grid impact of faults [1]. In such a method, detailed converter and (AC) grid models can be used for a more realistic representation of e.g. fault impacts or converter overcurrents. Automated test procedures could be developed to perform this validation once the initial protection system design has been completed.

For the case study in this chapter, a more limited validation of the design is performed. Additional fault locations for the component-level design are evaluated and compared to the originally assumed critical cases.

3.5 Case Study: Protection System Design for Offshore Electrical Energy Hub

This section presents the application of the protection system design methodology, as explained throughout this chapter, to a case study representing an offshore electrical energy hub. The considered grid consists of four (bipolar) cable connections and one offshore converter station, as illustrated in Figure 3.5. The DC grid is solidly grounded at the offshore converter station. Each converter is considered identical, operating at a voltage of ± 525 kV, with a nominal capacity per pole of 1000 MW. Relevant converter parameters for the component-level studies are listed in Table 3.6 [28].

3.5.1 Conceptual Design Outcomes

The conceptual method described in Section 3.2 is used to determine the ideal configuration of DCCBs. The main fault-impact metric is the worst-case loss of infeed, which represents the maximum loss of power transfer to connected AC grids. Four power flow scenarios are considered, as listed in Table 3.1. These represent different conditions in which the converters and cables in the

Figure 3.5: HVDC grid considered in the case study

Figure 3.6: Converter parameters for case study

Parameters	Value
Arm resistance	0.67Ω
Arm inductance	15 mH
Submodule capacitance	$6000 \mu\text{F}$
Number of submodules	276
Overcurrent threshold (K)	2 p.u.
peak rated arm current (\hat{i}_{arm})	2.07 kA
Peak rated AC current (\hat{i}_{AC})	2.87 kA
Peak rated AC voltage (\hat{v}_{AC})	244.95 kV

HVDC grid are operated at their maximum capacity, leading to the maximum LoI in case of faults.

Table 3.1: Active power injection into the HVDC grid (per pole) in pre-fault power flow scenarios

Scenario	OWF	AC Grid 1	AC Grid 2	AC Grid 3
PF1	0	-2000	1000	1000
PF2	1000	-2000	0	1000
PF3	1000	-2000	1000	0
PF4	0	2000	-1000	-1000

Given these power flow scenarios, the protection configuration shortlisting method can be applied using different DCCB counts. This results in a shortlist *lowest-impact-configurations*. Figure 3.7 shows the worst-case LoI in the selected lowest-impact-configurations for each DCCB count. With two or more DCCBs, the LoI is limited to 1000 MW for all power flow scenarios. Meanwhile, with one DCCB, only PF3 results in a higher fault impact.

It is assumed that allowing this higher fault impact in only one power flow scenario is an acceptable risk when compared to the cost of an additional DCCB. Therefore, the configuration shown in Figure 3.8 is selected for further use in this case study. However, the results show that, if a temporary LoI of 2000 MW is never allowed, two DCCBs are required in the DCSS.

3.5.2 Component Sizing Outcomes

The component-level detailed design sizes the DC reactors while considering the selected DCCB configuration. Since DCCBs are not placed at every line terminal (as would be the case in typical component-level studies that assume

Figure 3.7: Worst-case loss of infeed in lowest-impact-configurations selected by shortlisting method

a pre-defined protection strategy [43]), reactors can be considered either at line or converter terminals, or in series with the DCCB. Figure 3.9 shows the considered reactors in the DCSS. Knowing the DCCB configuration from the conceptual design, the key constraints for the protection system can now be specified for the critical components. Here, it is assumed that converter C_1 , which is located nearest to the DCSS, is critical for the design, as is the DCCB in series with reactor L_6 . The constraints for this case study can consequently be expressed as:

$$I_{C_1}(t) \leq I_{C_1,DC,max} \quad (3.7)$$

$$|I_{L_6}(t)| \leq I_{DCCB,max} \quad (3.8)$$

The current (I_{L_6}) through the DCCB can be calculated with Eq. (3.5). Consequently, the worst-case pre-fault power flow includes the maximum current through the DCCB in the direction of the fault, while the worst-case fault location is the one for which the voltage difference over L_6 is maximal. From Eq. (3.4) follows that the voltage at the cable terminal depends on the attenuation and the reflection of the voltage wave. Therefore, with a high reflection coefficient, the voltage difference at the cable terminal can reach up to 2 p.u. after the initial reflection, if attenuation is ignored. However, such a high reflection coefficient also implies a low transmission of the voltage wave to the busbars where the DCCB and converter of interest are connected. Consequently, in a system with high reflection coefficients (i.e. large termination reactors) at each cable, high inductances at the DCCB and the converter terminal are likely not necessary, as the voltage waves are not transmitted to the busbars.

On the other hand, the inductance can also be concentrated at the DCCB and converter terminal, instead of at the line terminations. In this case, for the considered grid topology, no reflections occur at the line terminations since traveling waves can freely propagate from one line to the other, because

Figure 3.8: Selected DCCB (indicated with red X) configuration and resulting protection zones

there are no inductors at the cable terminals. Now, the voltage at the DC busbar in the faulted protection zone is equal to the voltage at the terminal of the faulted cable, but the magnitude of this initial voltage deviation is only affected by the attenuation of the voltage wave. Therefore, it can be assumed that the critical fault location is at the cable termination near the DCSS, where the attenuation of the voltage wave is minimal.

Comparing these two extremes of concentrating all inductance either at the line terminations or at the DCCB and converter, it is reasonable to assume that concentrating the inductance in the DCCB reactor would be most attractive from a cost perspective. Therefore, for the initial inductor sizing in this case study, only L_6 is considered for guaranteeing the proper DCCB operation. The DCCB capabilities assumed in this case study are listed in Table 3.2. The considered operating time and maximum interruptible current are based on available literature [54, 68]. The nominal steady-state current through the breaker is assumed at 2.5 kA.

Table 3.2: DCCB parameters used for component-level design

	Parameter	Rating
t_{DCCB}	DCCB operating time	2 ms
$I_{DCCB,max}$	Maximum interruptible current	12 kA
$I_{DCCB,nom}$	Nominal steady-state current	2.5 kA

Figure 3.9: DC reactors considered in the component-level design

Using these parameters, an initial estimation of the required inductance value for L_6 can be made using Eq. (3.6), resulting in $L_6 = 110.5$ mH. This value is evaluated in EMT simulation, using Type 5 averaged value models for the converters (as defined in [66]) and frequency dependent cable models. The critical pre-fault power flow scenarios derived in Section 3.3.2, i.e. maximum DCCB current in the direction of the fault and maximum active and reactive power in critical converters, are considered. The simulation results confirm that the estimated inductance value leads to breaker currents below the maximum interruptible limit, as shown in Figure 3.10a. Moreover, Figure 3.10b shows that the DC terminal current in critical converter C_1 stays below the overcurrent limit for faults in the remote protection zone (Zone 2) allowing this converter to remain in continuous operation.

Since the calculation using Eq. (3.6) is expected to overestimate the required inductance by assuming a constant ΔV_L , the design can be refined by lowering the inductance values. The simulation results in Figure 3.11 show that an inductance of 95 mH suffices to prevent the maximum DCCB current from being reached. These simulations also showed that, for these tested inductance values, converter C_1 remains in continuous operation for faults in the remote protection zone. The order of magnitude of the found inductance corresponds with typical values found in other component-level studies for similar fault-clearing durations [28, 43].

(a) DCCB current for faults at 0 km in both protection zones (b) Converter C_1 DC current for fault in remote protection zone

Figure 3.10: Validation of DCCB and converter current in EMT simulation for $L_6 = 110.5$ mH

(a) Fault at 0 km in Zone 1 (b) Fault at 0 km in Zone 2

Figure 3.11: DCCB fault currents for different inductance values for L_6

3.5.3 Evaluation of Design

The component-level detailed design was performed using analytically identified critical fault scenarios. These are evaluated in this section by considering additional fault locations in simulation. The simulation results shown in Figure 3.12 illustrate the evaluation of the critical fault location in the fully connected system. This figure shows that, using the DCCB parameters and reactor values as designed in the component-level phase, faults at 0 km from the switching station do indeed lead to the most critical fault currents in the DCCB and critical converter in this case study.

Thus, it can be concluded from this evaluation that the selection of critical fault scenarios in the component-level design stage was adequate for the conducted reactor sizing study. However, further (system-level) evaluation

Figure 3.12: Fault currents for faults at different distances from the DCSS

studies, that are beyond the scope of this chapter, would have to be performed, using more detailed EMT models, to fully validate the protection system as designed in this case study. These additional validations include:

- The validation of the full protection sequence, including fault clearing and re-energizing
- Detailed analysis of the converter response (including checking arm current limits) during the fault clearing process, considering different control modes and settings
- Analysis of actual loss of power transfer and impact on AC grids using detailed models
- Evaluation of energy dissipation requirements in DCCBs
- Impact of DC reactor on dynamic system performance

3.6 Conclusion

This chapter illustrated a design methodology for protection systems in HVDC switching stations and electrical energy hubs. Dedicated design methods for conceptual and component-level design of these systems were summarized and applied to a case study. Due to separation of these methods into distinct design phases, each study could be conducted with a sufficient level of detail for the application, while being more flexible than typical design methodologies that require more assumptions in the design (e.g. by assuming pre-determined protection configurations). The case study results showed that the considered five-terminal HVDC grid can be protected

against unacceptable loss-of-infeed faults using one HVDC circuit breaker in the switching station. The evaluation of fault currents in EMT simulation validated the analytical reactor sizing estimations and identified critical scenarios. Future evaluation studies should also consider additional aspects in the evaluation, such as the full fault clearing sequence and grid restoration.

Chapter 4

Topology Optimization for DC Circuit Breaker Placement in HVDC Switching Stations

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- M. Van Deyck, T. Van Acker, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, “Topology Optimization for DC Circuit Breaker Placement in HVDC Switching Stations,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2606.14286*, 2026. [3]

4.1 Introduction

High voltage DC (HVDC) grids play a crucial role in the transition towards a decarbonized energy system. Their ability to transmit power over large distances is a key benefit for the integration of remote renewable energy sources and for grid reinforcement and interconnections [69]. Recent plans for new HVDC projects have increasingly shifted towards modular multilevel converter-based multiterminal HVDC grids that bring together several DC connections in *electrical energy hubs* (EEH) or DC switching stations (DCSS). This shift from point-to-point links to multiterminal connections increases the flexibility, efficiency and robustness [70]. Moreover, an integrated offshore multiterminal HVDC grid consisting of several offshore EEHs has been identified as a preferred solution for the integration and further development of offshore wind farms in the North Sea [71].

4.1.1 HVDC Protection

While the development of HVDC grids connected through DCSS is expected to improve socio-economic welfare and facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources [72], a key technical – and economic – challenge remains in the risk for high-impact contingencies in DC grids. This risk, which has been a key obstacle for the development of multiterminal HVDC grids for many years [70], stems from the nature of fault currents caused by DC-side short-circuit faults. Such fault currents are, due to rapid capacitive discharge of cables and converters in the DC grid and the lack of natural zero-crossings, impossible to interrupt with “traditional” switchgear as used in AC grid protection systems [32]. Therefore, a non-selective approach to HVDC protection has been applied in nearly all existing HVDC systems with only one exception currently operating in China [73, 74].

Non-selective protection systems typically rely on the interruption of fault currents at the AC-side of converters using AC circuit breakers. During this process, the converters bypass their internal power electronic components and capacitors to avoid damage, known as *blocking*. The converters then act as uncontrolled rectifiers into the DC grid [24]. During this period, the DC grid voltage cannot be maintained and there can be no controlled active power flow through the HVDC grid. Thus, the entire HVDC grid is temporarily unable to operate until the faulted element is cleared from the de-energized DC grid, after which the remaining healthy components can be restored to normal operation.

This non-selective approach to HVDC protection has proved sufficient for point-to-point, cabled HVDC systems. In these systems, any DC-side fault leads to the permanent outage of the entire link (or the faulted pole in case of pole-to-ground faults in bipolar systems with metallic return), and the speed and location of the fault interruption are of little consequence. However, the loss of an entire multiterminal HVDC grid, even for a short time, is likely to have an intolerably high impact on the frequency and voltage angle stability of connected AC grids [40]. Therefore, protection strategies that rely on HVDC circuit breakers (DCCB) to interrupt fault currents within the DC grid have been proposed. DCCBs facilitate selective fault clearing within the HVDC grid, allowing healthy DC grid elements to remain in continuous operation [26]. The need for such selective strategies has been identified for HVDC grids that consist of multiple offshore hubs [75] and in general for multiterminal HVDC grids [76]. However, although DCCBs are approaching technological maturity and global commercial availability [77], the cost of these components is expected to remain a significant barrier to their widespread implementation.

To mitigate the high investment costs required for a fully selective protection system that protects each element individually using DCCBs, a *partially*

selective strategy can instead be applied. This strategy relies on the use of fewer DCCBs, not to rapidly clear any faulted element from the rest of the system, but to split the grid into several protection zones, keeping the non-faulted zones in continuous operation and de-energizing and restoring the faulted zone. This temporary de-energization causes a temporary loss of power transfer capacity during the time between the fault interruption and the restoration of the non-faulted elements, after galvanic isolation of the fault at zero current. Following the DC grid restoration at the end of the fault clearing process, a permanent loss of power transfer capacity remains due to the isolation of the faulted element from the grid. In case of permanent DC faults, such as isolation breakdown in a cable, the permanent loss of power transfer capacity persists until the faulted element is repaired. Therefore, the selectivity of the DC protection system, defined by the placement of DCCBs, mainly impacts the magnitude of the temporary loss of power transfer during the fault clearing process, as illustrated in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Example representation of the total power transfer through an HVDC grid during the DC fault clearing sequence, assuming partially selective protection and automatic reconnection of converters after temporary stops (timings are indicative).

4.1.2 Problem Statement

The choice of a protection strategy is a fundamental aspect of multiterminal HVDC grid design. Several methods have been proposed to consider the trade-off between *investment cost* and the *AC grid frequency stability in case of faults* [1]. However, in the context of HVDC grids that consist of several links connected to a central substation - a DCSS or EEH - simply determining a protection strategy does not fully determine the design. For example, a large

DCSS could be “split” in many ways when applying the partially selective strategy, using different numbers of DCCBs in various configurations, as illustrated in Fig. 4.2. In fact, even if the number of DCCBs is determined in the design, thus fixing the expected investment costs, many possible configurations of the substation can still be achieved by arranging the DCCBs and busbar connections in different ways. Even with the same number of DCCBs, these different configurations could offer different levels of fault-impact-mitigation, depending on the power flows and anticipated faults in the HVDC grid [64]. Therefore, this chapter proposes an optimization method for the design of DCSS topologies, focusing on the placement - or *configuration* - of DCCBs, aiming to minimize the risk of temporary power imbalances caused by DC grid contingencies in all relevant operational scenarios.

Figure 4.2: Different possible ‘partially selective’ breaker configurations in an example EEH

4.1.3 Literature Review

The novelty of the proposed method, compared to existing optimization-based grid design methods, lies in the consideration of fault impacts caused by the transient power imbalance in the objective, while remaining fully flexible in the DCSS topology and protection system design. Typical optimization tools that consider the effect of contingencies on the grid operation, so-called Security-Constrained Optimal Power Flow (SCOPF) methods, focus on the steady-state operating point of the grid before and after relevant contingencies [78]. Although additional time-domain studies may be performed to validate the frequency stability of considered systems after a fault, or constraints ensuring stability can be included in these methods, they inherently focus on optimizing the operating point of the grid, e.g. by minimizing generation costs or losses, and are usually less focused on minimizing the impact

of faults through optimal protection system design [79]. Security constraints can also be included in the grid design stage, rather than the operational stage, in Transmission Network Expansion Planning (TNEP) problems, as proposed in [80] for hybrid AC and DC systems. Similarly to typical SCOPF methods, this optimization method focuses on steady-state aspects, such as the availability of connections after contingencies and the need for redundancy in the grid planning, rather than the design of protection systems, which do not influence the long-term availability of connections but impact the grid stability on a transient time scale.

Several studies have specifically considered the design of HVDC protection systems in an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) framework, evaluating the benefits of using DCCBs in multiterminal HVDC grids. In [81], the reliability, costs and losses of several HVDC grids with different protection system implementations are compared in order to determine the economic benefit of using DCCBs. This benefit is represented by the fact that DCCBs allow a more interconnected HVDC grid without risking the maximum Loss of Infeed (LoI) limit being exceeded in connected AC grids. Each case considered in this study is designed such that LoI limits in connected AC grids are always respected. In this regard, fault impacts caused by transient power imbalances are again represented only as a constraint while the benefit of DCCBs is considered in the possibility to connect more lines together while staying within this security limit. Similarly, [82] applies OPF calculations to compare a multiterminal HVDC grid using one DCCB to a similar system that is preventively decoupled when LoI constraints could be exceeded, thus evaluating the economic benefit of a selective protection system without considering the actual impact of transient power imbalances caused by DC faults.

A more detailed representation of fault impacts on the AC grid frequency stability is considered in the TNEP method presented in [76]. A frequency response model is used to represent the impact of DC faults under different protection strategies. The impact of DC faults is represented economically by the cost of reserves needed to mitigate AC grid imbalances and avoid under-frequency load shedding. In this way, the fault impact is compared to the expected investment costs of DCCBs. By representing the fault impact as a cost, the performance of the DC protection system can be considered in the objective of the optimization. However, the protection system itself is not fully flexible for design in [76], as only a fully selective and non-selective strategy are considered, without flexibility for the placement and number of DCCBs.

4.1.4 Contribution and Outline

As the AC grid inertia provided by conventional generators continues to decrease worldwide, designing protection systems based on existing LoI constraints, which ensure frequency stability can be maintained today, may not prove sufficient for the AC grid of the future. In this future system, transient power imbalances that are deemed acceptable in current grid codes may cause much more severe frequency instabilities due to the reduced amount of inertia. Therefore, when designing protection systems for multiterminal HVDC grids, optimizing the DCCB configuration to *minimize* possible fault impacts ensures the effectiveness of the protection system. Moreover, if the impact of transient power imbalances is represented by a cost, a cost-benefit analysis can be performed to determine the optimal number of DCCBs, which impose significant investment costs, resulting in optimal protection system configurations for HVDC switching stations.

Therefore, this chapter proposes a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization framework for the design of the topology and DCCB placement in HVDC switching stations, such that power imbalances caused by DC grid faults are minimized. The principles of the proposed method build on those used in [64], where an iterative, graph model-based method was used to shortlist DCCB configurations for specific EEH case studies. The optimization method discussed in this chapter formulates the principles governing the operation of HVDC protection systems in a structured mathematical framework. A risk-based design approach is presented and illustrated for a case study. This approach integrates aspects like the DC cable failure rate, DCCB costs and realistic power flow setpoints in the design of the DC protection system. Consequently, the optimization method proposed in this chapter forms the basis for a flexible tool for protection system design in HVDC switching stations, which can be adapted based on the needs of system developers and used for the cost-efficient development of secure HVDC grids in the future.

As indicated by the literature review, the combined focus on transient fault impacts in the objective and the fully flexible design of DC protection configurations differentiates this method from existing grid design methods. The proposed method also improves on existing expert-based design methods for HVDC protection systems which focus on selecting and implementing predefined protection strategies. In this chapter, a more flexible approach that leads to an optimal design is taken.

The conceptual principles and mathematical framework of the optimization problem are explained in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 then introduces a case study for the application of the method, followed by the discussion of the results in Section 4.4. Section 4.5 then draws conclusions and discusses future work.

4.2 Mathematical Framework

This section presents the mathematical framework for the DCCB placement optimization problem. This framework must accurately represent the operation of the DC grid and the protection system, before and during contingencies, as well the fault impact and the design constraints used to generate optimal DCSS topologies in the solution. Tab. 4.1 provides a general overview and generic examples of the notation used throughout this section to describe the formulation.

Table 4.1: Notation used for mathematical framework

element	notation	example
index	lower-case italic	x
set	calligraphic	\mathcal{X}
variable	sans serif	X
parameter	italic	X

4.2.1 Sets, Variables and Parameters

A DCSS is represented in the optimization problem by a graph $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ with vertices $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{I} \cup \mathcal{P}$ and edges $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}^i \cup \mathcal{E}^p$ (Fig. 4.3). Nodes are grouped into two unique subsets: external AC nodes $i \in \mathcal{I} \subset \mathbb{N}$, which are connected to the DCSS through a converter station and HVDC line, and internal DC nodes within the switching station $p \in \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{N}$. Similarly, the edges are also grouped into two unique subsets: connections $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$, i.e. DC cables and converters, between an external node i and a DC node p , and DC breakers $pq \in \mathcal{E}^p$ between two internal DC nodes p and q . As illustrated in Fig. 4.3, the connection set \mathcal{E}^i contains all edges ip for which $p \leq i$, which limits the number of binary variables and symmetrical solutions to the optimization problem. This reduction of the problem size stems from the assumption that all internal nodes $p \in \mathcal{P}$ can be considered as identical DC connection points in the DCSS. Moreover, as DCCBs are assumed to work bidirectionally, the set of breaker edges \mathcal{E}^p contains only edges pq for which $p < q$.

In addition to the node and edge sets, two other sets are defined: discrete points in time are denoted by $t \in \mathcal{T}$, and second, DC faults are denoted by $f \in \mathcal{F} = \mathcal{I} \subset \mathbb{N}$.

A binary variable x_{ip} is introduced for each possible connection $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$ to indicate whether it exists ($x_{ip} = 1$) or not ($x_{ip} = 0$). The power flow through a connection $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$ from external node i to internal node p at a time $t \in \mathcal{T}$ is denoted as $P_{ip,t}$ and as $P_{ip,t,f}$ for a given contingency $f \in \mathcal{F}$. Similarly, for each possible DC breaker $pq \in \mathcal{E}^p$, a binary variable y_{pq} and power flow

Figure 4.3: Illustration of the graph representing a DC switching station.

variables $P_{pq,t}$ and $P_{pq,t,f}$ are defined. The power flow through a breaker or connection is limited between P^{\min} and P^{\max} . Lastly, the net position of an external node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ at a discrete time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, i.e. how much power is demanded from or supplied to the DC grid at this node, is denoted as $P_{i,t}^{\text{net pos.}}$. Furthermore, for every AC node $i \in \mathcal{I}$, a power imbalance variable $P_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.}}$ is defined for every discrete time $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and contingency $f \in \mathcal{F}$. This variable can subsequently be split into positive and negative parts: $P_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.+}}$ and $P_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.-}}$, respectively. Note that at all times, at least either the positive or negative part should be zero.

4.2.2 Constraints

The constraints to the optimization problem, listed in (4.1)-(4.13), determine the design rules for the optimal DCCB configuration, while also representing the power flows and the operation of the DC protection system. It is determined by (4.1) that only one connection may exist between each external node and the DCSS. Subsequent constraints (4.2)-(4.4) enforce the power balance at the external AC nodes during normal and contingent operation, matching the flow through the HVDC grid (and any power imbalances) to the given net position in each time step. Similarly, (4.5) and (4.6) enforce the nodal power balance for the internal DC nodes.

EXTERNAL NODE CONSTRAINTS

converter per ext. node limit – $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } p \leq i} x_{ip} = 1, \quad (4.1)$$

normal operation power balance – $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } p \leq i} P_{ip,t} = P_{i,t}^{\text{net pos.}} \quad (4.2)$$

contingent power balance – $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}$:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } p \leq i} P_{ip,t,f} = P_{i,t}^{\text{net pos.}} + \mathbf{p}_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.}} \quad (4.3)$$

power imbalance – $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}$:

$$\mathbf{p}_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.}} = \mathbf{p}_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.+}} + \mathbf{p}_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.-}} \quad (4.4)$$

INTERNAL NODE CONSTRAINTS

normal operation power balance – $\forall p \in \mathcal{P}, t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} P_{ip,t} = \sum_{q \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } q > p} P_{pq,t} - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } q < p} P_{qp,t} \quad (4.5)$$

contingent power balance – $\forall p \in \mathcal{P}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}$:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} P_{ip,t,f} = \sum_{q \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } q > p} P_{pq,t,f} - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{P} \text{ if } q < p} P_{qp,t,f} \quad (4.6)$$

CONNECTION CONSTRAINTS

connection power limit – $\forall ip \in \mathcal{E}^i, t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$x_{ip} P_{ip}^{\min} \leq P_{ip,t} \leq x_{ip} P_{ip}^{\max} \quad (4.7)$$

$$- \forall ip \in \mathcal{E}^i, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F} :$$

$$x_{ip} P_{ip}^{\min} \leq P_{ip,t,f} \leq x_{ip} P_{ip}^{\max} \quad (4.8)$$

$$- \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, p \in \mathcal{P}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F} \text{ if } p \leq i \text{ and } p \leq f :$$

$$(1 - x_{fp}) P_{ip}^{\min} \leq P_{ip,t,f} \leq (1 - x_{fp}) P_{ip}^{\max} \quad (4.9)$$

DCCB CONSTRAINTS

DCCB count limit :

$$\sum_{pq \in \mathcal{E}^p} y_{pq} \leq N^{\text{cb}} \quad (4.10)$$

DCCB power limit – $\forall pq \in \mathcal{E}^p, t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$y_{pq} P_{pq}^{\min} \leq P_{pq,t} \leq y_{pq} P_{pq}^{\max} \quad (4.11)$$

$$- \forall pq \in \mathcal{E}^p, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F} :$$

$$y_{pq} P_{pq}^{\min} \leq P_{pq,t,f} \leq y_{pq} P_{pq}^{\max} \quad (4.12)$$

$$- \forall pq \in \mathcal{E}^p, k \in \{p, q\}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F} \text{ if } k \leq f :$$

$$(1 - x_{fk}) P_{pq}^{\min} \leq P_{pq,t,f} \leq (1 - x_{fk}) P_{pq}^{\max} \quad (4.13)$$

Connection constraints (4.7) and (4.8) pose boundaries on the power flow through connections $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$. In (4.9), the operation of the protection system is represented. This constraint enforces that, if a faulted connection $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is connected to a certain DC node $p \in \mathcal{P}$ (i.e. $x_{fp} = 1$), no power may flow, during contingent operation, through any connection ip connected to this DC node p . Consequently, (4.9) represents the operation of a DC protection system that de-energizes the entire faulted protection zone, represented here by a DC node, thus interrupting power flow through the connections to that node.

The maximum number of DCCBs in the switching station is constrained by (4.10). The constraints in (4.11) and (4.12) limit the power flow through breaker edges in normal and contingent operation respectively. Finally, (4.13) represents the opening of DCCBs, allowing no power flow through breaker pq if either p or q (denoted in (4.13) with the auxiliary index $k \in \{p, q\}$) is connected to the faulted line.

4.2.3 Objective function

Given the high costs of DCCBs, the optimization problem can be structured as a cost-benefit analysis to determine the optimal number of breakers to include – in an optimal configuration – in the DCSS. To this end, the total DCCB cost is compared to the *risk* related to power imbalances caused by DC faults. In (4.14), it is shown how this trade-off between investment cost and risk is represented in the objective function of the optimization problem. The first term in (4.14) represents the total capital costs for the time period \mathcal{T} , assuming a fixed cost c^{CB} per DCCB. The second term in (4.14) represents the total risk. The impact of DC faults is quantified using a cost for the positive and negative power imbalance ($c^{\text{imb.}+}$ and $c^{\text{imb.}-}$) for each external AC node. For every fault $f \in \mathcal{F}$, this cost-based representation of the impact is multiplied with the probability of this fault occurring (φ_f) during a given time step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ to represent the total risk. In this chapter, the probability of each fault is assumed constant in time, though variable failure rates could also be considered.

$$\min \sum_{pq \in \mathcal{E}^p} c^{\text{CB}} y_{pq} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}} \varphi_f (c_{i,t}^{\text{imb.}+} p_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.}+} - c_{i,t}^{\text{imb.}-} p_{i,t,f}^{\text{imb.}-}) \quad (4.14)$$

4.3 Case Study Description

This section presents the network and input data for the illustrative case study used to demonstrate the DCCB configuration optimization. A schematic rep-

representation of the considered network is given in Fig. 4.4. In the following subsections, the test case is described conceptually and linked to the parameters and sets used in the optimization problem.

Figure 4.4: Schematic representation of the case study network. Internal DC nodes \mathcal{P} are shown in red and external nodes \mathcal{I} are shown in blue.

4.3.1 HVDC grid layout

The presented case study considers an HVDC grid, containing a DCSS connected to six external AC nodes: $\mathcal{I} = 1 : 6$. The DCSS is assumed to be located offshore, in close proximity to two offshore wind farms, with identical generation profiles, represented by two external nodes: $i = 1$ and $i = 2$. The other external nodes represent onshore AC grids.

Every external AC node is connected to the DCSS by a bipolar HVDC converter station and cable, representing the connections $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$. These bipolar connections each have a total capacity of 2000 MW. However, as only pole-to-ground cable faults are considered in the case study, a single pole representation of the grid is used in the optimization problem. Therefore, the minimum and maximum power ratings can be expressed as $P_{ip}^{\min} = -1000$ MW and

$P_{ip}^{\max} = 1000$ MW, for all $ip \in \mathcal{E}^i$. Each external AC node is assumed to be located at a certain distance from the DCSS. Tab. 4.2 shows the lengths of connections between each external node and the DCSS.

Table 4.2: Lengths of connections from external nodes $i \in \mathcal{I}$ to the DCSS

External AC node	Length L_i [km]
$i = 1$	0
$i = 2$	0
$i = 3$	70
$i = 4$	100
$i = 5$	150
$i = 6$	700

4.3.2 Contingencies

The optimization problem considers a set of contingencies \mathcal{F} that, in this case study, represent pole-to-ground cable faults in the HVDC grid. The fault probability φ_f for each contingency can be derived from Mean Time To Failure (MTTF) data from literature [81, 83, 84]. The MTTF, typically expressed for HVDC cables in years/100 km, can be converted to the probability of a fault f occurring in any time step t through (4.15), where L_f is the length of the faulted connection (in km) and d_t the duration of any time step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ (in hours).

$$\varphi_f = \frac{1}{\text{MTTF}} \cdot \frac{L_f}{100} \cdot \frac{d_t}{8760} \quad (4.15)$$

For the example case study in Section 4.4.1, an example MTTF of 15 years/100 km is used [84]. Using a time step duration of $d_t = 1$ hour, this leads to a fault probability per time step of $\varphi_f = 7.61 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot L_f$.

Since the probability of DC cable faults depends on the connection length, and the DCSS is, in this case study, assumed to be close to the offshore wind farms represented by external nodes $i = 1$ and $i = 2$, the optimization problem can be simplified by not considering any faults on these connection. Consequently, instead of $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{I}$, the set of contingencies becomes $\mathcal{F} = \{3 : 6\} \subset \mathcal{I}$.

4.3.3 Pre-Fault Power Flows

The power flow variables in the optimization problem depend on the net positions in the external AC nodes, given by $P_{i,t}^{\text{net pos.}}$. These must be provided as input to the optimization problem for each node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and time step $t \in \mathcal{T}$. To gather this input data for the case study, a simple economic dispatch optimization was run using publicly available data and projections

of load and renewable energy source profiles, generation costs and installed capacities [72]. By including a variable that represents power import and export for each market zone in the dispatch model, the optimal power transfer through the HVDC grid is calculated for each time step $t \in \mathcal{T}$. Moreover, as the dispatch problem relies on data for European countries and market zones [72], the external AC nodes $i \in \mathcal{I}$ must be matched to the considered countries to match $P_{i,t}^{\text{net pos.}}$ to the results of the dispatch optimization. In the case study, the offshore wind farms represented by nodes $i = 1$ and $i = 2$ are assumed to be located near the Belgian coast. External nodes $i = 3$ and $i = 4$ represent different locations in the Belgian onshore grid, with identical demand profiles. Two other external grids are considered: $i = 5$ represents the GB power system and $i = 6$ the continental part of the Danish power system.

4.3.4 Fault Impact Cost Representation

To accurately represent the impact of transient power imbalances caused by DC faults – and affected by the DCCB configuration – the positive and negative imbalance costs $c^{\text{imb.}+}$ and $c^{\text{imb.}-}$ must quantify the monetary impact caused by the temporary loss of power transfer. This transient power imbalance could cause a large rate of change of frequency in AC grids, possibly leading to frequency instability. However, reserves markets meant to prevent such instabilities (FCR and aFRR procurement markets) are not fully suitable to represent the imbalance costs in this chapter. These markets are independent of the *occurrence* of a fault, and instead procure some amount of capacity for every market interval [85]. Alternatively, costs related to the *activation* of reserves (e.g. aFRR energy costs) do depend on the occurrence of imbalances in the grid [86]. However, the impact of the transient power imbalance caused by DC faults extends beyond the energy cost (which is expected to be relatively small due to the short duration of this stage in the overall fault clearing process, as illustrated in Fig. 4.1), as even short imbalances can affect frequency stability, depending on the magnitude of the imbalance and the AC grid inertia [40]. As a result, a detailed cost representation that accurately quantifies the impact of the occurrence of a transient power imbalance should be developed in future studies in order to use the proposed optimization method in a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis for the optimization of the DCCB count and configuration in a real system. However, since this is out of the scope of this chapter, example values for $c^{\text{imb.}+}$ and $c^{\text{imb.}-}$ are used for the illustration of the method. Tab. 4.3 shows how the positive and negative imbalance costs in each considered external node relate to the reference value $c^{\text{ref.}}$. Although it is possible to consider time-dependent imbalance costs, constant values are used here. In general, it is assumed for this case study

that negative imbalance costs are lower than positive imbalance costs. The positive imbalance cost for $i = 1$ and $i = 2$ is assumed relatively high since these external nodes represents offshore wind farms that cannot increase their power output in case of a fault. For external nodes $i = 3$ and $i = 4$, imbalance costs are assumed identical as these nodes are located near each other.

Table 4.3: Relative imbalance costs for each external zone

External AC node	$c_i^{\text{imb.}+} [c^{\text{ref.}}]$	$c_i^{\text{imb.-}} [c^{\text{ref.}}]$
$i = 1$	100	0.2
$i = 2$	100	0.2
$i = 3$	1	0.5
$i = 4$	1	0.5
$i = 5$	1.5	0.75
$i = 6$	0.75	0.3

4.3.5 DC Switching Station

Up to four DCCBs are considered in the case study, which means that $N^{\text{cb}} = 4$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{1 : 5\}$ in the optimization problem. The power flow through non-faulted DCCBs is limited by the constraints in (4.11) and (4.12). However, detailed considerations on the steady-state power flow capacity through DCCBs are out of the scope of this chapter. Therefore, these constraints are not considered in the case study.

Finally, the DCCB cost c^{CB} is an important parameter in the cost-benefit analysis. In the objective function, c^{CB} must present the total cost of a DCCB per time period considered in the optimization problem. Realistic values depend, therefore, on the total investment costs, the lifetime of the breaker, interest rates and operational costs. Since sufficient data for these values is not available in the public domain, the value of c^{CB} used in this chapter is also defined based on the reference cost $c^{\text{ref.}}$, as shown in Eq. (4.16). This value is subsequently varied in a sensitivity analysis in Section 4.4.2.

$$c^{\text{CB}} = 500 \cdot c^{\text{ref.}} \quad (4.16)$$

4.4 Case Study Results

This section presents the results of the breaker topology optimization method as applied to the case study described in the previous section. First, the risk-based cost-benefit analysis is performed to determine the optimal number of DCCBs and their configuration in the case study network shown in Fig. 4.4.

Second, a sensitivity analysis is performed on the DCCB cost c^{CB} and the fault probability φ_f to evaluate how these inputs affect the optimal placement and number of breakers in the DCSS.

4.4.1 Risk-Based Cost-Benefit Analysis

Using the given values from Section 4.3, the topology resulting from the solution to the optimization problem is shown in Fig. 4.5. One DCCB is used, creating two DC protection zones.

Although the connection to $i=6$ has the highest fault probability, due to the length of this connection, it is not fully separated in its own protection zone. Instead, another external node $i=4$ is connected to the same DC node, allowing uninterrupted power flow between these AC grids during faults on any of the connections to $p=1$. In this optimal solution, the AC node with the highest imbalance costs, $i=5$, is connected to the DC node with the lowest total fault probability.

For this result, the objective value amounts to $1386c^{\text{ref}}$. Given the assumed DCCB cost of $c^{\text{CB}} = 500c^{\text{ref}}$, this means that the breaker makes up 36.08% of the total cost, while the other 63.92% represents the fault impact risk.

4.4.2 Sensitivity Analysis

The solution of the risk-based cost-benefit analysis strongly depends on the applied cost values and the failure rates of the HVDC connections. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis is performed for these parameters.

First, the risk-based cost-benefit analysis is repeated for different values of c^{CB} (still expressed based on the reference cost c^{ref}). The result of this analysis, shown in Fig. 4.6, indicates that, if all other inputs and parameters are kept the same, the use of one DCCB in the configuration from Fig. 4.5 is optimal for breaker costs between $100c^{\text{ref}}$ and $850c^{\text{ref}}$. For higher breaker costs, it becomes optimal to not include any DCCBs, accepting the total fault impact risk of $1752c^{\text{ref}}$. Moreover, this sensitivity analysis shows that for DCCB costs lower than $100c^{\text{ref}}$, it becomes optimal to include a second or third DCCB in the DCSS. Fig. 4.7 shows the optimal DCCB configurations for these breaker counts.

The optimization method can be used to calculate the total risk for different numbers of optimally configured breakers. This total risk is represented by the second term of the objective function in (4.14). Based on these results, shown for up to four DCCBs in Tab. 4.4, the *marginal benefit* of each DCCB can be calculated based on how much each additional DCCB reduces the total fault-impact risk in the case study, when optimally configured.

Figure 4.5: Optimal DCCB configuration for the considered DC switching station

Figure 4.6: Optimal number of DCCBs based on the breaker cost

The total fault-impact risk results listed in Tab. 4.4, which determine the marginal benefit of DCCBs, are subject to the considered fault probabilities.

Figure 4.7: Optimal DCCB configurations when 2 or 3 DCCBs are selected

Table 4.4: Fault-impact risk for different numbers of optimally configured DCCBs in the considered case study.

DCCB count	Total risk [$c^{\text{ref.}}$]	DCCB marginal benefit [$c^{\text{ref.}}$]
0	1752	-
1	886	886
2	800	86
3	723	77
4	697	26

These probabilities are calculated in (4.15) based on an example MTTF for HVDC cables. Therefore, since the risk calculated in the objective function is proportional to the assumed failure rate, higher MTTF values decrease the value of DCCBs for risk minimization in the DCSS. For example, if a MTTF of 50 years/100 km is considered, as proposed in the *best case* scenario in [81], no DCCBs would be implemented in the result of the optimization problem (assuming a cost of $500 c^{\text{ref.}}$), since the total risk without any breakers amounts to $525.6 c^{\text{ref.}}$ and the use of one optimally configured DCCB reduces the risk only to $265.8 c^{\text{ref.}}$. Fig. 4.8 shows the optimal DCCB count based on the considered failure rates for different breaker costs.

Figure 4.8: Optimal number of DCCBs based on DC cable MTTF for different breaker costs

4.5 Conclusion

The proposed method for HVDC circuit breaker (DCCB) configuration optimization in HVDC switching stations (DCSS) offers a novel approach to conceptual HVDC protection system design. The connectivity of external connections to the DCSS and the arrangement of DCCBs within the DCSS is optimized to minimize protection system costs and the total fault-impact risk. Consequently, this method ensures that future HVDC grids can be developed with cost-effective protection systems, optimized for case-specific operating conditions. This improves on the current practice that relies on general, pre-defined protection strategies. Moreover, the consideration of fault-impact risk in the objective function allows protection systems to be optimized beyond current maximum loss-of-infeed limits, ensuring the effectiveness of these systems in the future, when the reduction of conventional generation capacity might cause these limits to change.

The optimization method was applied to a case study with six external connections using pre-fault power flow scenarios representing one year of operation, calculated using economic dispatch optimization. While the specific outcomes discussed in this chapter are case-study specific, it can be concluded that the proposed method is generally applicable for calculating the optimal number of DCCBs in a DCSS, while also determining the optimal configuration thereof. Additionally, the conducted sensitivity analyses of the DCCB costs and DC cable failure rates provide a clear view of how these parameters influence the optimal DCCB count and the total fault-impact risk. Consequently, the proposed method can serve not only as a tool for optimal DCSS design, but is also useful for studying the benefits of selective

DC protection systems conceptually.

In this paper, the optimization problem considers a single, centralized DCSS. Future extensions of the formulation could include the co-design of multiple switching stations to represent meshed multiterminal HVDC grids. Moreover, for the industrial application of this method, it is possible to include detailed, time-dependent representations of imbalance costs and fault probability.

Chapter 5

Hybrid Analytical-EMT Method for HVDC Protection System Component-Level Design

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- A. Mohammadi, M. Van Deyck, G. Chaffey, D. Van Hertem, “Hybrid Analytical-EMT Method for HVDC Protection System Component-Level Design,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2605.11174*, 2026. [4]

5.1 Introduction

Multiterminal HVDC systems provide a promising solution for future transmission networks, enabling bulk power transfer over long distances, interconnection of asynchronous AC systems, and integration of offshore wind farms [11]. Therefore, the industry is increasingly looking toward large-scale HVDC grids to transmit energy across Europe and to achieve the required expansion in electricity transmission capacity [87]. However, one of the main technical challenges in HVDC grids is protection against DC faults. Due to the characteristics of DC fault currents, such as the absence of natural current zero crossing and a rapid rise rate, dedicated protection devices such as a DC circuit breaker (DCCB) for interrupting fault currents, and a DC inductor for limiting the fault current may be needed for multi-terminal HVDC systems [11, 43]. Protection systems that allow DC-side fault isolation help avoiding prolonged interruptions of power transfer, ensuring continuity of supply, and maintaining the operation of the healthy parts of the grid [38].

System-level protection design, which includes the specification of the

system topology, protection strategy and converter DC fault ride-through (DC-FRT) capabilities [1, 88], provides inputs for the component-level design. In this component-level design stage, key protection system parameters, such as DCCB characteristics and fault current limiting inductance, are specified to meet the system-level and component-level requirements [1, 43, 44]. Component-level design for multi-terminal grids is not straightforward, as components, such as DCCBs, DC inductors, and converter control systems, are interdependent [28]. Therefore, detailed electromagnetic transient (EMT) modeling is typically required for these studies. In industrial applications such as the Zhangbei project [89], DC inductors installed in series with DC-CBs are reported in the range of 150–200 mH to limit the DC fault current. Other studies propose inductances exceeding 500 mH for this purpose [28, 90]. Large inductance values increase installation costs [91] and may lead to stability issues [92, 93]. Therefore, DC protection systems should be properly designed to account for these effects by sizing DC inductors as small as possible while still satisfying protection requirements.

Existing design methods take different approaches, which can be categorized into three main groups. The first group is based on analytical solutions, such as fault-current estimation [94–97]. Such methods have been used for DC inductor sizing [44] and DCCB parameter specification [43]. However, analytical methods cannot suitably represent the complex behavior of the HVDC system [98]. In practice, representing components such as HVDC cables or converters fully analytically is impractical and overly complex [98], as details are often unavailable due to IP concerns and black-box representations [58]. The second type of design method, such as [99, 100], is based on exhaustive EMT simulations. Although these methods can be more representative of system and component behavior, in practice, relying solely on EMT simulations to design components often requires extensive, repetitive simulations, with hundreds to thousands of iterations, depending on the system size. The third category uses hybrid methods, a combination of methods and tools, to tackle the problem. For instance, in [29], optimization-based methods are used to size the DC inductor optimally. These methods embed an EMT model into an optimization problem to optimally size components and represent system behavior more accurately. However, these optimization problems require expensive EMT simulations, particularly as the system size increases towards future large-scale multi-terminal HVDC systems.

In this chapter, an efficient hybrid method for designing protection components is proposed. An overview of the proposed method is illustrated in Fig. 5.1. The method first identifies critical design scenarios to reduce the number of simulation cases. Then, a hybrid methodology is applied, where combination of analytical approximations and EMT model allowing accurate specification of the component parameters. The main contributions of this

Figure 5.1: Overview of the protection component sizing method

chapter are as follows:

- Development of a computationally efficient, systematic method for sizing protection components for both fully and partially selective DC protection systems.
- Identification of critical cases to reduce the number of simulations for the design, increasing the efficiency of the design process.
- Achieving high-accuracy component parameter specification using the proposed hybrid analytical–EMT method, with the possibility of incorporating vendor models.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows. Section II outlines the protection systems requirements, followed by the component-level design method in Section III. Section IV describes two case studies, and Section V discusses the results.

5.2 Protection System Functional Requirements

5.2.1 System-Level Requirements

System-level functional requirements of HVDC protection systems have recently been developed [1, 32, 38, 43]. Key system-level design aspects include the loss-of-infeed limits of the surrounding AC grids [38], the selection of protection strategies and zone configurations (i.e., fully selective, partially selective, or non-selective) [1, 32], and the converter DC-FRT requirements [38, 43]. These requirements should be specified during the system-level protection design stage to ensure that high-level objectives, such as the stability of the surrounding AC and DC grids, are maintained [1]. Therefore, in this chapter as shown in Fig.5.1, the fundamental inputs requirements form system-level design for component-level design are as follows:

- System topology and configuration

- Protection strategy and protection zones boundaries
- Converter DC-FRT requirements

5.2.2 Component-Level Requirements

The design of the selected components must ensure that the protection system can effectively isolate faults while satisfying the individual component constraints, such as DCCB and converter maximum current capacity [32]. While the system-level design provides the system-level constraints, there is flexibility in the sizing of the individual components that make up the protection system, to achieve the same system-level requirements. In this chapter, component-level design is considered to be the sizing or specification of any individual components. This chapter focuses primarily on components that are co-dependent and require co-design [1]. These include DC inductor size, converter overcurrent capacity, and DCCB parameters such as operation time and DC fault neutralization time (sum of DCCB internal commutation time and protection relay time) [43, 44, 90]. Other protection related components, such as protection algorithm constraints, instrument transformers, and other primary equipment, may not necessarily require co-design, and are hence not considered in the examples in this chapter – although the method could be extended to include other components where deemed relevant.

5.3 Deriving Component-Level Design Constraints

This section presents the derivation of the necessary analytical approximations to represent the component-level functional requirements and constraints used in the design method.

To meet the protection component-level design objectives, several variables can be adjusted. DCCB operation time, DC reactor size, and converter overcurrent capacity are all co-dependent and should each be considered in the design stage. For example, assuming the converter's overcurrent capability is fixed, a larger inductor or a faster circuit breaker can be used to meet all design objectives. Although there are other novel fault-current handling methods, such as [101, 102], this report relies on more industrially relevant technology.

The DCCB operation time [103, 104] and converter overcurrent capacity [28] are generally limited to a certain range due to technical constraints in industrial technology. Hence, the DC inductor size is considered in this chapter as the primary design variable. First, the component-sizing method is developed for a single protection zone, and then a more general approach is derived.

Figure 5.2: A HVDC grid for component sizing for a single zone

5.3.1 Converters Functional Requirements and Constraints

For converter DC FRT requirements, according to [39], converters in the healthy zone may be required to remain operational (continuous operation), temporarily block, or permanently block following a DC fault. This chapter primarily considers the first option, in which no converter is allowed to block in the healthy zone, as this imposes more stringent conditions on the converter and DC inductor [43]. Otherwise, converters will not impose requirements on DC inductor sizing.

As an input from the system-level design, it is assumed that the system topology with DCCBs is known. A generic HVDC grid is shown in Fig. 5.3, where the grid is divided into multiple protection zones by DCCBs. For the design of a single protection zone, the method focuses on one zone (Zone 1), while the other zones are represented in an aggregated manner. Although having only a converter in Zone 1 and directly connected to the DCCB can be considered as a worst case [105] to say connected during the fault, adding additional converters and cables within Zone 1 makes the method sufficiently general to represent both partially and fully selective strategies. Hereafter, the term ‘zone’ refers to a protection zone. Furthermore, the inductor in the system is assumed to be located in series with the DCCB, as shown in Fig. 5.3.

To size the inductor based on converter limits, the relationship between the DC inductor current and the converter current must be approximated. Following a fault in Zone 2, the cables and converters in other zones feed current into the fault, through the DC inductor L_{dc} . Therefore, the DC inductor current can be approximated as $I_L = I_{con} + I_{cab} + I_{in}$, which consists of converter current I_{con} , connection cable capacitive discharge current I_{cab} , and the infeed current from the adjacent cables and zones I_{in} . The represented aggregated infeed current (I_{in}) and connection cable capacitive discharge current (I_{cab}), rather than relying on a simplified analytical solution, can be measured from a detailed EMT model.

By applying a fault in Zone 2 along the cable, the voltage at bus B can be

approximated using (5.1) for the time window of interest, i.e., the neutralization time (t_n). This time is the sum of the protection relay time and the DCCB internal current commutation time ($t_n = t_{relay} + t_{cb}$) [106].

$$U_B \approx L_{dc} \frac{\Delta I_L}{t_n} + U_C \quad (5.1a)$$

$$\Delta I_L \approx \Delta I_{in} + \Delta I_{cab} + \Delta I_{con} \quad (5.1b)$$

In this equation, ΔI_L is the change in the inductor current over the interval t_n , where ΔI_{in} and ΔI_{cab} represents the change of infeed and connection cable current changes, and ΔI_{con} is the converter DC side current change over the given period. U_C is the cable-end voltage on Bus C, which highly depends on the cable parameters, the inductor value, and the fault location. The cable voltage envelope can be estimated by simulating various fault locations along the DC cable and taking the minimum of average voltage as $\bar{U}_m = \min(\bar{U}_C, 0)$, where \bar{U}_C is cumulative average of U_C [90]. It is worth noting that \bar{U}_m value depends on the the time instance. The process of finding \bar{U}_m is elaborated in subsection 5.3.3.

Considering Fig. 5.3, U_B can also be expressed as (5.2) by applying KVL from the converter location to bus B. The converter resistance and the connection cable resistance are assumed to have a negligible impact. To maintain the continuous operation of the converter, its control should remain active during fault neutralization. Therefore, in (5.2), it is assumed that the converter behaves as a voltage source and its terminal voltage is U_{dc} , equal to the nominal value [28]. In (5.2), $L_{eq} = L_{con} + L_{cab}$ and $L_{con} = (2/3)L_{arm}$ is the converter equivalent inductor from terminal and L_{cab} is the lumped inductance of the connection cable.

$$U_B \approx U_{dc} - L_{eq} \frac{\Delta I_{con}}{t_n} \quad (5.2)$$

Based on (5.1) and (5.2), the DC inductor for converter requirement, L_{dc}^{con} , can be expressed as:

$$L_{dc}^{con} \approx \frac{(U_{dc} - \bar{U}_m^{t_n})t_n - L_{eq}\Delta I_{con}}{\Delta I_{con} + \Delta I_{in} + \Delta I_{cab}} \quad (5.3)$$

Considering (5.3), ΔI_{in} and ΔI_{cab} are measurements that come from the EMT model used to approximate the inductor value, while the other parameters are grid parameters that are assumed to be known. To size the minimum inductor to meet the converter requirements, ΔI_{con} needs to be set to its critical value. The worst-case set point corresponds to the converter operating at its rated current in rectifier mode (I_{con}^r) with maximum reactive power, leading to the critical value of $\Delta I_{con}^c = I_{con}^m - I_{con}^r$. The converter DC terminal current limit (I_{con}^m) can be derived based on its arm current limit as (5.4) [28], where K is the converter overcurrent factor or per-unit blocking threshold, i_a^r

is the rated peak arm current, and i_{ac}^{max} is the maximum AC current limit on the converter side. Equation (5.4) is modified to use i_{ac}^{max} instead of the rated AC current to account for the actual AC current contribution. Here, i_{ac}^{max} is a limit imposed by the converter current controller [66].

$$I_{con}^m = 3 \left(K i_a^r - \frac{i_{ac}^{max}}{2} \right) \quad (5.4)$$

Based on (5.3), parameters such as overcurrent capacity, maximum AC current limit, protection relay delay, and DCCB technology affect the critical inductor value. Furthermore, it is evident from (5.3) that the system configuration affects the required inductor value. For example, a lack of adjacent cables (ΔI_{in}) and connection cable (ΔI_{cab}) results in a large value for L_{dc}^{con} . Overall, the converter requirements may impose a minimum inductance requirement for the DC inductor.

5.3.2 DCCB Requirements and Constraints

As the DCCB current should not exceed its maximum limit, the inductor in series with the DCCB must be designed to meet this constraint. According to (5.1), considering the maximum voltage difference across the inductor and substituting the critical value of ΔI_L provides an approximation of the critical inductor value. For the maximum voltage difference $\Delta U = U_B - \bar{U}_m$, U_B is assumed constant and equal to the nominal system voltage, and \bar{U}_m is the cable voltage envelope that accounts for the traveling wave effect. The critical value for the current change is $\Delta I_L^c = I_{cb}^m - I_{cb}^r$, where I_{cb}^m and I_{cb}^r are the DCCB maximum current limit and rated current, respectively. As a result, the critical inductor size based on the DCCB requirements is approximated by (5.5), where a lower maximum current limit, a longer operating time, and a higher rated current result in more stringent requirements for the inductor value.

$$L_{dc}^{cb} \approx \frac{U_{dc} - \bar{U}_m^{t_n}}{I_{cb}^m - I_{cb}^r} t_n \quad (5.5)$$

5.3.3 Critical Cases for Design

For component-level design, it is essential to identify the critical operating conditions of components and base the design on them. This approach ensures that the selected design parameters remain valid across all relevant scenarios while minimizing the total number of cases that need to be evaluated.

5.3.3.1 Critical Converter

Within each zone, a critical converter that reaches its overcurrent limit faster than the others for out-of-zone faults must be identified. According to equation (5.3), the critical converter in a zone depends on both system configuration, such as line parameters, and also converter parameters as shown in (5.4). In equation (5.3), the assumption of zero infeed current ($\Delta I_{in} = 0$) and zero cable discharge current ($\Delta I_{cab} = 0$) corresponds to a worst-case condition for the converter. Accordingly, this case requires the largest inductor to prevent blocking within the fault neutralization time. Therefore, the critical converter in each zone is identified as the one requiring the largest inductor. For instance, if two converters in a protection zone have the same parameters, the one connected directly to the DCCB or via the shortest line is the critical one due to the low fault wave propagation delay and low ΔI_{cab} [105]. Once the critical converter for each zone is identified, the corresponding infeed current can be determined in the system.

5.3.3.2 Critical Power Flows

The identification of critical power flows in the system is relatively straightforward. The power flows that result in the maximum loading of the critical converter in rectifier mode and the maximum loading for the DCCB under study, are considered critical power flows with regard to a DC-side fault [43].

5.3.3.3 Critical Fault Type and Location

The critical fault type depends on system configuration and grounding options, e.g., a pole-to-ground (P-g) fault in a bipolar system is a possible fault for a cable-based system with zero fault resistance [32, 107]. The worst-case fault location is the one that results in a rapid rise and high peak fault current. Due to the traveling-wave effect, the reflection coefficient, the cable parameters, and fault neutralization time, it is possible that a critical fault location lies along the cable in the other zone [67].

To find the critical fault location along the cable, a fault is applied at various locations. Then, the cable voltage envelope can be estimated by taking the minimum of the average voltage as $\bar{U}_m = \min(\bar{U}_C, 0)$, where \bar{U}_C is the average of cable end voltage at bus C (U_C) as shown in Fig 5.3.

As shown in Fig. 5.4, the critical fault location depends on the fault neutralization time (t_n) and the critical time (t_c) where $\bar{U}_m \leq 0$. For $t_n \geq t_c$, a terminal fault (0 km) results in a minimum voltage envelope ($\bar{U}_m = 0$) and a high fault current after the critical time (e.g., $t_c = 1.8$ ms in the illustrated case with example cable parameters). However, if $t_n < t_c$, a non-terminal fault should be considered as the critical fault location, and the minimum

Figure 5.3: A test HVDC system for identifying critical fault location

Figure 5.4: Critical fault location along the cable according to cable voltage envelope (\bar{U}_m)

cable end voltage at (\bar{U}_C) the t_n instant correspond to critical fault location along the cable. This critical time (t_c) depends on parameters such as cable characteristics and the DC inductor, and it must be determined for each system using a similar approach as shown in Fig. 5.4. It is worth noting that although a large DC inductor can result in smaller \bar{U}_m and increase the t_c , it more limits the fault current. In summary:

- Different fault locations along the cable are simulated in EMT-type software, as shown in Fig. 5.3. For each case, the average cable-end voltage (\bar{U}_C) is calculated. As a post-processing step, the voltage waveforms should be aligned by applying an appropriate time shift.
- The voltage envelope (\bar{U}_m) and the corresponding critical time (t_c) are then estimated as shown in Fig. 5.4.
- Based on the neutralization time of the protection system (e.g., DCCB technology):

- If $t_n \geq t_c$, the terminal fault is considered the critical fault location.
 - If $t_n < t_c$, the critical fault location possibly located somewhere along the cable. In this case, the minimum value of \bar{U}_C at t_n corresponds to the critical fault location.
- Note that having adjacent cables (to bus C in Fig. 5.3), reduces the t_c compared to when no adjacent cable is considered, and it makes the terminal fault more dominant critical location, which is easy to study. Therefore, when for the condition that $t_n < t_c$ and there is adjacent cable(s) to the bus, it is recommended to consider both terminal fault and identified critical fault along the cable as critical locations.

Note that although a large inductance can increase the traveling-wave effect and increase the critical time, it further limits the fault current. Therefore, a moderate inductance value is recommended, e.g. 100 mH.

To identify the critical fault location along a cable that causes a rapid rise in the fault current, a single cable connected to a converter through a DC reactor is considered, as shown in Fig. 5.3. This configuration is adopted for several reasons, as outlined below. Additionally, it is assumed that all cables in the system have identical properties. Otherwise, the analysis would need to be performed separately for each cable with different properties.

- Considering a fault in the cable with zero fault impedance results in a short circuit of the rest of the system, and no reflection occurs from the fault point. This implies that there is no influence from the part of the system located on the other side of the fault location.
- Having adjacent cables (connected to bus C in Fig. 5.3) to the cable under study reduces the reflection of the traveling wave at the line end by lowering the terminal surge impedance compared to the case where they are no adjacent cables. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 5.5, where adding an adjacent cable to bus C causes \bar{U}_C to shift upward and reduces the critical time from $t_c = 1.8$ ms (without an adjacent cable) to $t_c = 1$ ms (with an adjacent cable).
- Furthermore, this approach simplifies the analysis of the critical fault location in the system.

5.4 Component-Level Design Algorithm

After identifying the system-level and component-level requirements of the protection system, the protection component can be designed and specified to satisfy them. This section applies a hybrid analytical and EMT simulation-based approach.

Figure 5.5: Critical fault location along the cable according to cable voltage envelope (\bar{U}_m) when considering a adjacent cable to bus C in Fig. 5.3

5.4.1 Core Component Sizing Algorithm

The key design parameters for the system are the converter overcurrent capability, the DCCB current-interruption capability, the operation time, and the DC inductor value. Due to the interdependence among these parameters [90], the inductor value is treated as the output in this chapter. The others are treated as inputs to the algorithm, as their ranges are limited by current DCCB and converter technologies. The core algorithm for single DC inductor sizing is shown in Fig. 5.6 and described below.

5.4.1.1 Part A – System-Level Requirements and Critical Cases Identification

As a starting point, the system topology must be known, with protection zones and their boundaries primarily defined by the DCCB locations. The DC-FRT requirement for each converter is specified in a system-level study. In this chapter, it is assumed that converters in the healthy zone are not allowed to block. Otherwise, from the converter perspective, there will be no hard constraints on the DC inductor [43]. Furthermore, the critical converter, power flow, and fault type and location are identified at this stage using the methods presented earlier in Section 5.3.3.

Figure 5.6: Core component sizing algorithm for a single inductor

5.4.1.2 Part B – Iterative Analytical and EMT Design

This part of the method iteratively approximates the DC inductor size based on analytical calculations and EMT simulations to satisfy both the converter and DCCB requirements. In (5.3), all parameters are known, while ΔI_{in} and ΔI_{cab} are obtained iteratively from EMT simulations to approximate the inductor value. Initially, assuming $\Delta I_{in} = 0$ and $\Delta I_{cab} = 0$, the preliminary value of L_{dc}^{con} can be estimated. If the DCCB requirement is more restrictive ($L_{dc}^{con} < L_{dc}^{cb}$), there is no need to proceed with the EMT simulation in Part B. Otherwise, since (5.3) provides a conservative estimate (due to $\Delta I_{in} = 0$ and the absence of connection cable discharge current between the converter and

the fault location), an iterative simulation approach is used.

By updating ΔI_{in} and ΔI_{cab} , which depend on the grid configuration (and may be zero), the new value of L_{dc}^{con} is recalculated using (5.3). Part B is terminated when (5.6) is met, where ε is the tolerance between two successive values (e.g., 5%) and 'i' indicates the iteration number. After some iterations, Part B converges to an L_{dc} value that satisfies (5.3) and (5.5). However, the designed inductor in Part B may still be conservative (i.e., its value can be further reduced), as several simplifications were made in deriving (5.3) and (5.5). Thus, further refinement of the inductor value may be in Part C.

$$\frac{|L_{dc}^{con(i)} - L_{dc}^{con(i-1)}|}{L_{dc}^{con(i-1)}} < \varepsilon \quad (5.6)$$

In this design method, any converter model can be used. Consequently, it provides a promising approach when black-box models and industrial vendor models with unknown control implementations are utilized. However, it is important to note that certain converter parameters, such as S , i_{ac}^{max} , and K , must be known to apply the proposed method.

5.4.1.3 Part C – Final Refinement and KPIs

Upon deriving the analytical method, several simplifying assumptions were made in (5.3) and (5.5). The converter internal voltage is assumed as a constant-voltage source with an inductor, and a lumped inductor is used for modeling the connection cable as shown in Fig. 5.3. In (5.5), the voltage across the inductor is assumed constant and equal to the nominal system voltage. These assumptions may lead to an overestimation of L_{dc} . Since the proposed method uses the EMT models with a detailed representation of these components, the design parameter is iteratively fine-tuned to meet the design requirements.

To quantify whether the converter and DCCB requirements are met while the L_{dc} is minimal, a current margin KPI is used as shown in Fig. 5.7. It is defined as the difference between the maximum current limit and the current achieved with the designed inductor. For the converter, this is based on the arm current, as shown in (5.7), and for the DCCB, it is based on the DCCB current, as shown in (5.8).

$$\Delta I_{con}^{kpi} = \frac{K i_a^r - i_a^a}{i_a^r (K - 1)} \quad (5.7)$$

$$\Delta I_{cb}^{kpi} = \frac{I_{cb}^{max} - I_{cb}^a}{I_{cb}^{max} - I_{cb}^r} \quad (5.8)$$

Based on (5.7), i_a^a is the achieved peak arm current across all six arm currents when the sized L_{dc} is used. In (5.8), I_{cb}^{max} is the DCCB current limit,

Figure 5.7: Current margin criterion for inductor refinement

I_{cb}^r is the rated DCCB current, and I_{cb}^a is the achieved DCCB current when using the sized inductor.

The final criterion in Part C is the minimum of (5.7) and (5.8), which identifies the limiting component as defined in (5.9). A value of $\Delta I^{kpi} = 0$ indicates that the current has reached its maximum allowable limit. Therefore, the current KPI should satisfy the condition $0 \leq \Delta I^{kpi} < \Delta I_{target}$. As shown in Fig. 5.7, ΔI_{target} is a target that the algorithm aims to meet by reducing the DC inductor size. Additionally, it can also serve as a design margin. In each iteration, the new value is obtained using $L_{dc}^{new} = L_{dc}(1 - \alpha)$, where $0 < \alpha < 1$ is the reduction rate. To achieve faster convergence in Part C, a dynamic reduction rate is used instead of a fixed one. A large value of α increases the convergence rate, but it also increases the risk of a large step reduction that may violate the KPIs. Thus, a safe value for that is recommended as $\alpha \leq 40\% \Delta I^{kpi}$.

$$\Delta I^{kpi} = \min\left(\Delta I_{con}^{kpi}, \Delta I_{cb}^{kpi}\right) \quad (5.9)$$

5.4.2 Generalized Component Sizing Algorithm

To demonstrate an effective design for a generic system with multiple protection zones, a conceptual system with N protection zones is considered (Fig. 5.8), where neighboring zones are separated by a DCCB and an inductor. A generalized method for protection component design that accounts for the requirements of multiple protection zones is presented in Fig. 5.9. Initially, inductors in the system are set to values that satisfy the series DCCB requirements based on (5.5). In the next stage, for two proxy protection zones (directly connected via a DCCB), the inductor is designed using the core algorithm shown in Fig. 5.6. The converter requirements apply only to

Figure 5.8: Conceptual HVDC system with N protection zones

Figure 5.9: Generalized inductor design method for protection systems with multiple protection zones

zones that contain converters. For instance, considering Fig. 5.8, to design the inductor L_{12} , a fault is applied in Zone 2, and the inductor is designed based on Fig. 5.6. Here, $C_{ij} = 1$ means protection zone i is connected to zone j with a DCCB. Otherwise $C_{ij} = 0$. The same process is applied for Zone 2 to determine L_{21} . Therefore, the final inductor value is set to the maximum of

two values.

After designing the first DC inductor between two zones, the newly designed inductor is updated and replaced with its initial value in the system, and the process is repeated for the remaining inductors until all are designed. Additionally, the initial values of nearby inductors impact the target inductor value. To account for this interdependency during design so that the initial value of the nearby inductor has less impact on the designed inductor, an additional iteration is included in the final stage of the algorithm (Fig. 5.9) for the final inductor design. In this iteration, the previously designed values are used as initial inductor values.

5.5 Case Studies

5.5.1 Case Study Description

To demonstrate the application of the proposed method, two case studies are presented in this chapter, as shown in Fig. 5.10. In Case Study 1, a five-terminal bipolar system with a partially selective protection strategy is used. This system is divided into three protection zones by two DCCBs in series with DC inductors. Conversely, in Case Study 2, a four-terminal bipolar system with a fully selective protection strategy is evaluated. In both case studies, it is assumed that a suitable system-level design has already been carried out, providing DCCB locations as inputs to this component design stage. The half-bridge modular multilevel converter (HB-MMC), currently the preferred topology in industry [102], is employed in this study, with all converters sharing the same parameters and technology. Detailed system and converter data are provided in Table 5.1.

The key design parameters are K , I_{cb}^{\max} , t_{cb} , and L_{dc} . Table 5.2 presents different possible values for the key design input parameters (resulting in different design scenarios), considering some viable parameters for industrial DCCBs [103, 104] and converter overcurrent ratings [28, 102].

5.5.2 Component Models

The systems are modeled in the EMT environment (PSCAD). The cables are modeled by a frequency-dependent (phase) model for 525 kV. The converters utilize a Type 5 (average) model [66] in these example cases, though vendor models could be used for an industrial study. Additionally, a typical control scheme is implemented for the converters, including outer-level controls (such as DC voltage droop and active power controllers) and inner-level controls (such as a circulating current suppression controller with typical parameters) [108]. Furthermore, internal overcurrent protection is incorporated

Figure 5.10: Schematic per-pole diagram of considered case studies: (a) Case Study 1 partially selective protection strategy, (b) Case Study 2 fully selective protection strategy

into the converters [28, 102]. For the DCCBs, a Type 5 model [109] is adopted, utilizing generic data for the metal-oxide varistors (MOVs) [110]. The AC grids are represented by Thevenin equivalents with specified short-circuit ratios. The simulation time step is $20 \mu\text{s}$.

5.6 Results of Component Sizing for Case Studies

Table 5.1: System and component parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Rated apparent power (per pole)	S	1034	MVA
Rated active power (per pole)	P	1000	MW
Rated DC voltage	U_{dc}	525	kV
Rated AC voltage (converter side)	u_{ac}	273	kV (rms)
Rated peak arm current	i_a^r	2.2	kA
Converter AC current limit	i_{ac}^{max}	1.2	pu
Converter overcurrent rating	K	1.5–2	pu
Converter arm resistance	R_{arm}	0.4	Ω
Converter arm inductor	L_{arm}	15	mH
Submodule capacitance	C_{sm}	6000	μF
Number of SM per arm	N	276	–
DCCB current rating	I_{cb}^r	3	kA

Table 5.2: Considered key input design parameters

Converter	DCCB	
K	I_{cb}^{max} (kA)	t_{cb} (ms)
1.5, 2	12, 24	2, 3, 5

5.6.1 Case Study 1: Partially Selective Protection Strategy

Component sizing for Case Study 1, shown in Fig. 5.10 (a), is performed using the generalized algorithm shown in Fig. 5.9. In this Case Study, the grid is divided into three protection zones [64], each separated by a DCCB in series with a DC inductor. Regarding converter DC-FRT requirements, it is assumed that converters in the healthy zone must remain active and not block during an out-of-zone fault. Since all converters have identical parameters (Table 5.1), the converter directly connected to the DCCB, or the one connected through the shortest line, is considered critical in each zone. Thus, C_1 in Zone 1, C_3 in Zone 2, and C_4 in Zone 3 are the critical converters. In general, (5.3) and (5.4) can be used to identify the critical converter when the converters have different parameters, as explained in subsection 5.3.3. The critical power flows that result in maximum loading for the critical converters and DCCBs are identified in Table 5.3. A positive converter active power setpoint indicates rectifier mode. In the example considered, converter C_1 connects to an offshore wind farm, so its minimum active power setpoint is zero. Additionally, it is assumed that converters C_2 and C_5 operate in DC-voltage droop control mode. The critical fault type is considered to be a pole-to-ground (P–g) fault with zero fault resistance [38]. Although the traveling-wave effect [67] can cause a fast rise in fault current during a short

Table 5.3: Critical converter setpoints for each protection zone and their corresponding inductor design (Case Study 1)

Zone	Inductor	Converter active power setpoint (pu)				
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
1	L_{12}	+1	-	-1	-1	-
2	L_{21}	0	-	+1	+1	-
2	L_{23}	+1	-	+1	-1	-
3	L_{32}	0	-	-1	+1	-

Table 5.4: Inductor design results for Zone 1 requirements considering different input parameters (Case Study 1)

Scen.	Input parameters			Zone 1 L_{12} (mH)	KPIs	
	K (pu)	I_{cb}^{\max} (kA)	t_{cb} (ms)		ΔI_{con} (%)	ΔI_{cb} (%)
1	1.5	12	2	165	5	31
2	1.5	12	3	235	4	30
3	1.5	12	5	414	3	33
4	2	12	2	109	32	2
5	2	12	3	161	30	4
6	2	12	5	267	5	4

time window for non-terminal faults (Fig. 5.4), a terminal fault causes the highest fault current given the operation time of the chosen DCCBs (at least 2 ms). Thus, the critical fault location in this Case Study is at the terminal of the adjacent cable on the other zone, resulting in $\bar{U}_m = 0$ in (5.3).

5.6.1.1 Inductor Sizing to Meet Zone 1 Requirements

To illustrate the application of the core algorithm in Fig. 5.6, it is first applied to Zone 1 to size L_{12} to satisfy the protection requirements of this zone. Accordingly, the corresponding critical power setpoints from the first row of Table 5.3 are selected. For a P-g fault at the beginning of cable 3 (bus B_2), the algorithm is executed for some input sets, and the resulting values of L_{12} are summarized in Table 5.4. According to the results, the DC inductor size varies depending on the input sets. Scenario 3 with $L_{12} = 414$ mH and Scenario 4 with $L_{12} = 109$ mH require the largest and smallest inductor, respectively. Based on the current margin KPIs, it is evident that the method successfully sizes the inductor to achieve the target threshold margin ($\Delta I_{target} = 5\%$). Considering the competent constraint, depending on the input sets, the converter arm current is a limiting factor in scenarios 1–3 ($\Delta I_{con}^{kpi} < \Delta I_{cb}^{kpi}$), while in Scenarios 4–6, the DCCB constraint becomes a limiting factor.

In Fig. 5.11, the results of Scenario 1 are presented in detail. Plot (a) shows

Figure 5.11: Converter as a limiting factor, evaluated at $L_{12} = 165$ mH (Scenario 1 of Case Study 1)

that Part B of the algorithm converges to approximately $L_{dc} = 182$ mH after three iterations. However, due to simplifications in the analytical formulation, further refinement is carried out in Part C, where its final minimum feasible value of $L_{dc} = 165$ mH. As shown in plot (b), the algorithm terminates after five iterations, when the converter current margin meets the target threshold. Plots (c) and (d) show the converter arm current and DCCB current, respectively, evaluated with the final $L_{dc} = 165$ mH, demonstrating that the converter arm current approaches its limit first.

On the other hand, Fig. 5.12 presents the result for Scenario 4, where the DCCB constraint is the limiting factor ($\Delta I_{cb}^{kpi} < \Delta I_{con}^{kpi}$). Comparing the results of Scenario 1 and Scenario 4, the former converges to its final value in five iterations, whereas the latter converges in only two iterations.

5.6.1.2 Inductor Sizing to Meet all Zones Requirements

As shown in Fig. 5.10(a), the system consists of three zones and two inductors. Each inductor must meet the requirements of both connected zones. Specifically, L_{12} is determined by considering the requirements of both Zone 1 (associated with L_{12}) and Zone 2 (associated with L_{21}). Similarly, L_{23} is designed based on the requirements of Zone 2 and Zone 3 (associated with L_{32}). In total, the core algorithm (Fig. 5.6) should be executed four times per input set. The results of inductor sizing for all considered input parameters in Table 5.2 with respect to all protection zones are provided in Table 5.5. The

Figure 5.12: DCCB as a limiting factor, evaluated at $L_{12} = 161$ mH (Scenario 4 of Case Study 1)

final values for the two inductors in the system are in the last columns.

According to the results in Table 5.5, considering the final inductor value L_{12}^f , in all considered input parameters, Zone 1 requirement is the limiting one, as it requires a larger value of inductor (L_{12}) compared with the L_{21} . The reason is that the critical converter in Zone 1 (C_1) is directly connected to DCCB, whereas the critical converter in Zone 2 (C_3) is connected to DCCB through a 250 km cable. The connection cable reduces the required inductor value, as indicated in (5.3). In addition, due to the propagation delay of the cable, the contribution of C_3 to a fault in Zone 1 is delayed. This delayed response further alleviates the inductor requirement. For the second inductor (L_{23}^f), looking at the values for L_{23} and L_{32} , it is clear that the critical zone determining the final inductor value can vary depending on the input parameters. This highlights the need for a design based on all protection zones, as it is not always clear which is the primary limiting zone. Furthermore, when the number of nearby inductors is no more than one, such as Case Study 1, the effect of interdependency between the inductors is low, and therefore, there is no need for the final step in Fig.5.9.

5.6.2 Case Study 2: Fully Selective Protection Strategy

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method for a meshed system with a fully selective protection strategy, Case Study 2 is considered, as shown in Fig. 5.10(b). In this case, there are ten DCCBs, each in series with a DC

Table 5.5: Final inductor design results for Case Study 1

Scen.	Input parameters			Zone requirements (mH)				Final (mH)	
	K	I_{cb}^{\max} (kA)	t_{cb} (ms)	L_{12}	L_{21}	L_{23}	L_{32}	L_{12}^f	L_{23}^f
1	1.5	12	2	165	101	105	98	165	105
2	1.5	12	3	235	144	156	164	235	164
3	1.5	12	5	413	306	404	283	413	404
4	1.5	24	2	165	70	87	99	165	99
5	1.5	24	3	236	111	157	164	236	164
6	1.5	24	5	414	218	404	283	414	404
7	2	12	2	109	92	82	94	109	94
8	2	12	3	161	128	114	132	161	132
9	2	12	5	267	200	177	215	267	215
10	2	24	2	80	37	43	49	80	49
11	2	24	3	122	64	78	96	122	96
12	2	24	5	254	127	168	176	254	176

inductor and nine protection zones. Regarding DC-FRT requirements, none of the converters are allowed to block during out-of-zone faults. All four converters are critical to their respective zones. With regard to critical power flows, to design inductors L_1 to L_5 , converters C_1 and C_2 should operate in rectifier mode at rated power, while for L_6 to L_{10} , converters C_3 and C_4 should be in rectifier mode at rated power. This means that, in total, two sets of power flows should be considered.

Using the algorithm outlined in Fig. 5.9, the resulting inductor sizes are shown in Fig. 5.13. In this Case Study, $I_{cb}^{\max} = 12$ kA and $K = 2$ are held constant, while three values of t_{cb} are considered. Furthermore, in each scenario, all DCCBs in the system are assumed to be identical.

Fig. 5.14 shows the arm current of converter C_2 and the current of the DCCB in series with inductor L_5 for the three scenarios. When a fault occurs in cable 4, the sized inductors sufficiently limit the rate of rise of the fault current, ensuring that both the converter and DCCB requirements are met. Additionally, Fig. 5.15 investigates the impact of the fault location along the cable, where a P-g fault is applied along cable 3, and the arm current of converter C_1 , along with the current of the DCCB in series with L_2 , are monitored. These results correspond to the $t_{cb} = 5$ ms scenario, which imposes the most demanding conditions on the inductor. The results confirm that a terminal fault produces the highest fault current, and the sized inductors correctly limit it below the limits.

Figure 5.13: Final inductor design results for Case Study 2 based on Fig.5.9

Figure 5.14: Impact of various scenarios on (a) converter C_2 arms current and (b) DCCB current connection with L_5 , for a fault at beginning of cable 4 from C_2 (Case study 2)

Figure 5.15: Impact of fault location on (a) converter C_1 arms current and (b) DCCB current for $K = 2$, $t_{cb} = 5$ ms, $I_{cb}^{max} = 12$ kA with different fault location along the cable 3 from C_1 (Case study 2)

5.6.2.1 Impact of System Configuration and Nearby Inductors

As shown in (5.3), the infeed current from adjacent cables to the converter affects the inductor value. A higher number of adjacent cables increases the infeed current, thereby reducing the required inductance. For example, according to Fig. 5.13, L_1 has a smaller value than L_4 , which can be explained by the impact of two adjacent cables, while L_4 is influenced by only one adjacent cable (for $t_{cb} = 3, 5$ ms).

Additionally, there is an interdependency between nearby inductors. The higher the inductance of a nearby inductor, the more it limits the infeed current during a fault and requires a higher inductance. However, inductors that are far away have less impact on the local inductor value. This interdependency is addressed in the proposed algorithm in Fig.5.9.

5.6.2.2 Impact of Converter Control Mode

A comparison between L_4 and L_6 in Fig. 5.13 reveals that they share almost identical conditions regarding the number of adjacent cables and converter parameters, except for the converter control mode. Converter C_3 operates under DC voltage (droop) control (V_{dc}), whereas converter C_2 operates in PQ control mode. The results for this Case Study indicate that voltage control requires a larger inductor value than active power control. However, it is worth noting that different control implementations and parameters may yield different results. Therefore, further investigation into this aspect is required in future work.

Figure 5.16: Number of simulations required for sizing the component of a single protection zone

5.6.3 Efficiency of the Method

By utilizing the hybrid method, the proposed approach significantly reduces the number of required simulations compared to simulation-based methods [29, 99, 100], where the number of estimated required iterations is in the order of hundreds to thousands, and it can take a few days to finish [29], depending on the case study. In the proposed method, as shown in Fig. 5.16, the number of EMT iterations for sizing a single DC inductor varies across scenarios, with a maximum of 6. The average number of simulation iterations per scenario for Cases Sduies 1 and Cases Sduies 2 is 9 and 88, respectively, which can take a few minutes to an hour to run. According to the generalized algorithm in Fig. 5.9, the number of executions of the core algorithm (Fig. 5.6) and the total number of simulation iterations depend on the number of DC inductors and critical converters in the system.

Furthermore, identifying the critical simulation cases in subsection 5.3.3 can significantly reduce the number of required simulations and improve the design process's efficiency. For example, if a single critical fault location is identified and used as the design basis, it eliminates the need to evaluate multiple alternative fault locations. This approach simplifies the design while ensuring that it is based on the critical conditions.

5.7 Conclusion

A hybrid analytical-EMT method was proposed for systematically specifying protection component parameters in HVDC grids. The method ensures that the protection system requirements and component constraints are satisfied. It can be used for both partially and fully selective protection strategies. Two measures were used to enhance the efficiency of the method. First, critical cases were identified to reduce the number of design scenarios, thereby improving the efficiency of the design process. Second, a hybrid analytical-EMT

approach was adopted, in which the analytical part initializes and guides the EMT simulations, resulting in faster convergence and fewer simulations – orders of magnitude faster for the considered case studies. The proposed method provides high-accuracy results by directly incorporating detailed component models. In particular, the possibility of using vendor models ensures high-fidelity results. Depending on the system-level and component-level requirements and constraints, such as DCCB technology, the required DC inductor can vary. In the considered case studies, the inductance varied between around 50 and 450 mH.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Conclusion

This report presents a methodology that can be generally applied to electrical energy hubs or systems with similar characteristics to efficiently develop effective HVDC protection systems. Three design phases (system-level conceptual design, component-level detailed design and system-level performance evaluation) have been defined based on a review of protection system design methods in the literature. The application of the method in Chapter 3 illustrates the division and key interfaces between the different phases.

Novel methods have been proposed for system-level conceptual as well as component-level detailed design. The phased structure of the overall methodology allowed these new methods to be developed, tested and illustrated independently, each with a focus on different key design aspects. Because of this, the methods proposed in Chapters 4 and 5 focus on achieving an effective design of specific parts of the protection system, without relying on strong assumptions or detailed consideration of other relevant aspects. The integration of system-level and component-level methods into a sequential design methodology showcases the inherent complementarity of the design outcomes, which follows from the definition of the design phases in Chapter 2. Moreover, additional protection system aspects not considered at these levels are evaluated in the final system-level performance evaluation stage of the design. Although, in this report, no dedicated method is proposed for this design phase, it remains essential for the validation of the combined outputs of the previous stages, and for the evaluation of additional aspects of the protection system. For this reason, *Deliverable 6.2* focuses fully on this design phase for the case study of the Belgian energy island.

The focus of the protection system design methods presented in this report is primarily on electrical energy hubs, as their functionalities, challenges and opportunities have been specifically considered. However, the overall methodology, as well as the dedicated design methods are expected to be generally applicable with only limited modifications. Therefore, this report serves both as a practical guideline for protection system design in electrical

energy hubs, and as a framework and structure for the continued development of new and efficient methods for protection system design for HVDC grids generally.

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